

FUTURE MIGRATION
SCENARIOS FOR EUROPE

Case Study

UKRAINE

Drivers and Trajectories of Migration to Europe

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1. Introduction

Objectives and Justification of the Study

Ukraine is a country marked by a long tradition of migration. The aim of the report is to present analysis of internal and international migration trends in contemporary Ukraine before the outset of the Russian invasion in February 2022. Although the war has already disrupted previous migration trends and led to the unprecedented waves of refugees leaving the country and for the moment of writing it is impossible to predict how the situation would develop, we believe that the report can still be of use as it presents migration processes and their determinants captured during a specific time frame. Moreover, as it is stressed in the report, forced migration dates back to 2014 with huge numbers of IDPs leaving their homes in Donbas and Luhansk regions as well as Crimea.

The disproportions of socio-economic development of the regions of Ukraine significantly affect migration flows within the country. Our research has focused on Kyiv as a main migrant-receiving region in Ukraine. Kyiv is a capital of Ukraine, and is regarded as an important economic, political, and cultural centre and a hub for regional or international connections, commerce, and communication. It consistently demonstrates high indicators of socio-economic development, and is the most attractive destination for internal migrants in terms of residential as well as circular and pendulum migration. The report focuses primarily on the period of 15 years until 2021, but it also takes into account some previous relevant factors that have affected the migration dynamics. It takes into account the complexities of the decision-making process, shedding light on the interrelated factors. It presents migration processes as embedded in both structural contexts and subjective aspirations and sensibilities.

Contents of this Report

The aim of the report is to present the context for understanding the complexities of migration processes in Ukraine from the point of view of historical processes and then migrants' decision-making to move internally or internationally or to stay. It discusses the main findings of the qualitative research conducted in the frame of the FUME project in Ukraine. Following the executive summary, migration scenarios and patterns for Ukraine are presented, including both historic and contemporary dimensions. Next part focuses on various dimensions of migration, which enable us to better understand the motives, patterns and determinants of human mobility of Ukrainians. In particular, environmental, demographic, socio-cultural, economic and political aspects will be explored. That will be presented alongside the methodological note on the research process and interview sample. After that theoretical part, research's findings will be presented and contextualised. This part presents the reasons why internal migrants who live in Kyiv left their places of origin. Then, migrants' motives for choosing the capital as the place of settlement is explored. Afterwards, the report presents a tentative typology of migrants in terms of their intentions to stay or to migrate further. The report ends with conclusions.

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Last but not least, special thanks go to the reviewers who have carefully read the report and suggested some improvements, in particular to prof. Oleksiy Pozniak, the Head of the Migration Studies Sector of Ptoukha Institute for Demography and Social Studies of National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Dr. Tina Polek, Ph.D., member of the Center for Applied Anthropology in Kyiv, Dr. Julia Buyskykh from the Institute of History of Ukraine and the Centre for Applied Anthropology.

Executive summary

The report „Drivers and Trajectories of Migration to Europe. Ukraine case study” is a result of the FUME project “Future Migration Scenarios For Europe” which seeks to understand the patterns and modalities of migration by exploring, among others, the specificity of four case studies which represent diverse regions characterised by high immigration rate: Ukraine, Iraq, Senegal and Tunisia. The in-depth analysis of quantitative and qualitative data would contribute to the models aimed at providing possible future scenarios of migration to Europe as they elaborate on the complexity of interrelations between historical, economic, cultural, social and demographic factors in migration decision-making.

The Ukrainian case study is based upon qualitative study encompassing 30 semi-structured interviews and a focus group (both conducted in 2021), complemented by an analysis of secondary data related to migration and existing academic literature. Kyiv with its suburbs was chosen as the research locus, because it is the political and business centre of Ukraine and thus it attracts a lot of internal migrants from all over Ukraine. Key findings regarding various dimensions of migration are presented below.

Regarding the demographic dimension, population growth is not a driver of migration as the trend in Ukraine is reverse: since the 1990s the country has experienced population decline. However, demand for education is among the main motives behind migration. Educational opportunities provided by larger cities, and in particular the capital, influence the decision of young people to change their place of residence. There is a lot of interest among Ukrainians in receiving higher education abroad, usually in the EU. Poland is particularly attractive in this regard because of the close distance, lower costs of living than in Western Europe and - for Ukrainians with Polish roots - opportunities for free tertiary level education.

Economic factors play a pivotal role in internal and international migrations. The Regional Human Development Index for Ukraine shows significant discrepancies between regions. The most migrant-sending regions (excluding those occupied by Russia) are at the bottom of the ranking (either in low-middle or low groups of development). The capital city which attracts the most internal migrants ranks 1. The lack of jobs or the low level of salary were given as important factors in leaving one’s place of origin. In many provinces, especially in rural areas and smaller towns, average salaries are often too small to cover daily expenses. In Kyiv the opportunities for jobs and

higher earnings are much more common. The capital's labour market is also more diversified and offers work in many sectors of the economy which enables it to match qualifications with job offers. The supply of skilled jobs in the capital - and some other large cities - is an important driver for internal migrants. It is linked with increasing aspirations for career and self-development among the younger generation.

Unlike in other countries under investigation in the project, environmental dimension is for the moment not a major motive for migration. Neither degradation nor climate change-related extreme events were included in migrant's narratives explaining their mobility decisions. Among Ukrainian interviewees, only air pollution - either radioactive or from industrial activities - was mentioned a few times as one of many factors influencing decisions on migration.

As far as the governance dimension is concerned, the study shows evidence of its influence on migration trajectories, both internal and international. In Ukraine, the introduction of visa-free movement to EU countries in 2017 accounts for the lack of narratives about irregular migration among our interviewees. Political factors emerged as migration drivers after 2014 in relation to Russia's annexation of the Crimean peninsula and armed conflict in the eastern regions of Ukraine (Donbas region). Following those events, Ukraine has encountered a mass population exodus from the aforementioned regions to the state-controlled territories. Thus a significant number of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) has emerged. The annexation of Crimea also deteriorated the economic situation for the non-Russian population. This situation, however, may change in the near future due to the evolution of the political situation.

In migration studies, societal dimension is another key factor influencing people's mobility. Social networks in Ukraine are an important source of knowledge of employment opportunities. In many cases, it plays a role in the initial phase of migration (help with accommodation, finding a job, etc.). Most of all, however, it influences the choice of destination. Social media groups connecting migrants from a particular place are increasingly used by potential migrants.

Internal migrations are also partially driven by cultural factors. In some cases, for people from rural areas or small towns, the atmosphere of big cities with a perceived wider level of freedom and tolerance play a role. The religious freedoms are very important for members of religious minorities fleeing occupied territories where numerous organisations are banned and their members face persecution (e.g. Jehova Witnesses or members of Hizb ut-Tahrir) Women emancipation which plays an important role in other origin countries, in Ukraine was not mentioned as a determinant of migration.

The perception of the attractiveness of the EU lifestyle is not obvious and depends on the cultural background and information promoted by other migrants. For some groups of the younger generation, especially the highly skilled professionals it may play a role in encouraging them to migrate to Europe. There is a wide perception among the Ukrainian population that the general standards of education in the EU are higher. Additionally, the problem of corruption in the educational sector remains unresolved.

Existing and historical migration scenarios to and from Ukraine

Before the Declaration of independence proclaimed in 1991, Ukraine was subject to population mobility in the countries to which it belonged, i.e., Russian, Austro-Hungarian Empires and the USSR. The first wave of Ukrainian emigration dates back to the late XIX - early XX century that corresponds to the period of mass emigration from Europe to the New World. This migrant outflow was from Western Ukraine known as Galiciya, which was part of Austro-Hungarian Empire, where up to 10% of the population left for America (Malynovska, 2016, p. 17).

From the Central and Eastern Ukraine that were part of the Russian Empire, the emigration routes went eastward, i.e. beyond the Urals, and in 1895-1913 at least 1.6 million people left Ukraine towards the Russian Far East (Ibid.). During the same period, immigrants from the Volga region of Russia moved to the industrialised regions of Ukraine, in particular to Donbas.

The second wave of population mobility occurred in the interwar period and encompassed economic, political and forced migration. During that period marked by industrialization and collectivization a new type of migration developed – involuntary economic migration, when the labor force was directed to development of remote areas. The more severe form of forced migration, namely deportations also occurred during this period. The massive man-made famine in Ukraine 1932–1934 or “Holodomor” (extermination by hunger) was also an important driver of forced migration. The famine in rural areas forced its inhabitants to seek food in cities, where many of them died (Table 1).

Table 1. Components of rural in- and out-migration in Ukraine, 1927–1938.

Migration stream	Period	Direction of stream	Migrants
Rural to urban internal migration	1927–1938	rural to urban within Ukraine	-3,388,000
Eviction of kurkuls (farm owners) to settlement areas	1930–33	rural to outside Ukraine	-364,000
Prisoners to concentration camps	1929–38	rural to outside Ukraine	-285,000
Forced emigration of peasants	1929–33	rural to outside Ukraine	-576,000
Deportation of Poles to Kazakhstan	1936	rural to Kazakhstan	-60,000
Emigration of Jews	1929–38	rural to outside Ukraine	-57,000
Resettlement of peasants from Russia and Belarus to Ukraine	1933–34	Russia and Belarus to rural	138,000
Organized resettlement of peasants	1929–30	rural to outside Ukraine	-80,000
Resettlement of kurkuls from Central Asia to Ukraine	1931	Central Asia to rural Ukraine	16,000
Labor emigration from rural areas	1935–38	rural to outside Ukraine	-170,000
Total net rural migration	1927–38		-4,826,000

The third wave took place after the WW2 and included different types: forced evacuation and refuge of wartime; repressive deportations from the Western Ukraine (in 1939-1940, up to 1 million people were deported, in 1944-1952 - over 200 thousands) and from Crimea between 200 to 400 thousands Crimean Tatars; direction of the labour force for the development of virgin lands, construction projects, natural resources mining in Siberia and Kazakhstan (Ibid.). The reverse direction of the labour force from Russia and other former Soviet republics also took place, in particular to repopulate Crimea.

The organised demographic processes in Ukraine during the Soviet period were aimed at collective identity construction informed by the ideological concept of 'Soviet people'. The majority of organised migrants in Ukraine during the Soviet was made of graduates of vocational, secondary special and higher educational institutions, which had to work at least three years in jobs where assigned by government agencies (Malynovska, 2013, p. 159-160).

According to recent research, during the last decade before the collapse of the USSR, the annual migration turnover between Ukraine and the rest of the USSR was about 1.5 million with a persistent positive migration balance. The main migrant-sending regions were Kazakhstan, other Central Asian republics, the North Caucasus and the Central Black Earth Region as well as Transcaucasia (Vollmer, Malynovska, 2016, p. 21).

It is worth mentioning that during the Soviet period population mobility was severely restricted, in particular it applied to rural-urban migrations. In the late 1920s, peasants began to flee en masse to the cities to escape forced collectivization. To control rural-urban migration in the USSR internal passport (identity card) was introduced in 1932. Initially it was issued only to residents of cities and new workers' settlements who reached 16 years of age, as well as civil servants and employees of state farms. Most of the rural population was deprived of this opportunity; they were enrolled in the collective farm from the age of 16 and could not go further than the district centre without a written permission from the collective farm management. Unauthorised leave was punishable by a fine, and repeated violations were criminalised and punishable by up to three years in prison. Rural inhabitants were first allowed to issue passports only in 1974.

The external mobility was also strictly controlled by the state. To leave the country, it was necessary to obtain a so-called exit visa. It was accompanied by complicated bureaucratic procedures, including authorization by superiors at work, by heads of the local party and trade union committees, then by district committees and in some cases by secret police KGB. These restrictions lasted until 1991. The fourth wave of emigration has taken place since 1991, and has primarily socio-economic nature. It has resulted in the formation of new Ukrainian diasporas, in particular in the Russian Federation, Central and Southern Europe, and in North America. Other patterns include 'ethnic migration' and repatriation, in particular the emigration of Jewish population to Israel, Germany and USA, and the return of Crimean Tatars to their historical homeland. Since 2014, following the annexation of Crimea by Russia and armed conflict in the Donbas region, Ukraine has encountered en mass population exodus from the aforementioned regions to the state controlled territories. Thus a significant group of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) has emerged.

According to the UN Department of Economic and Social Affairs report, as of 2017 there are 5,5 international migrants from Ukraine (compared to 4.9 million in 2000), which is about 11 % of the total population (UN, 2017). According to the estimations by the Centre for Economic Strategy, 6.3 million people left Ukraine between 2002 and 2017, and about half of them moved to the West. The other sources report that the number of Ukrainians who simultaneously work abroad is between 3 million (Libanova, 2018) and 2.6–2.7 million people (Piontkivska I. et al., 2018). Most of them are temporary and circular workers.

The dynamics and a high level of fluctuations in cross-border mobility are visible in the World Bank data which is based upon the United Nations Population Division. World Population Prospects (Figure 1). Net migration, defined as the total number of immigrants minus emigrants, for Ukraine shows how migration patterns have changed in recent years. While in 1992 it was a net immigration country, a few years later it became net emigration. Between 2002 and 2007 the trend reversed once again, and nowadays the number of people migrating to Ukraine is greater than those who leave the country.

Figure 1. Net migration – Ukraine 1990 – 2020 both sexes combined (thousands).
Source: United Nations Population Division. World Population Prospects: 2019 Revision, after: World Bank 2020.¹

According to the State Statistic Service of Ukraine, the most attractive country for Ukrainian labour migrants in 2017 was Poland - 38,9 % of total migration, followed by Russia – 26,3 %, Italy – 11,3 %, Czech Republic – 9,4 %, Portugal – 1,6 %, Hungary – 1,3 % (Mihratsiia, 2019, p.8).

Regarding emigration, there is a continuous increase in the number of Ukrainians who migrate to Europe. Altogether, residence permits issued by EU countries are growing. The number of all valid permits equalled almost 1.3 million, while the first permits reached almost 757 000 in 2019 (Figure 2). The introduction of the visa-free regime for Ukrainian citizens in 2017 contributed to this trend and has had a visible impact on international migration (IOM 2019).

¹ The empirical data used here includes estimates of population and components of demographic change (fertility, child, adult and overall mortality, international migration). See: <https://population.un.org/wpp/DataQuery/> These data include Crimea. Total population and distribution by age and sex estimated to be consistent with the population by age and sex of the 2001 census, official estimates through 2018, and with estimates of the subsequent trends in fertility, mortality and international migration. International migration based on: estimates derived as the differences between overall population growth and natural increase.

Figure 2. Number of the UE first residence permits and valid residence permits for Ukrainians.

Source: Eurostat, Asylum and Managed Migration, <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/asylum-and-managed-migration/data/database>. (Blue: first residence permits, red: valid residence permits).

Eurostat estimations based on the number of issued residential permits indicated the main destination countries in EU for Ukrainian labour migrants in 2018 as follows (Eurostat , Asylum and Managed Migration):

- Poland – 442 thousand;
- Italy – 224 thousand;
- Czech Republic – 132 thousand;
- Germany – 121 thousand;
- Spain – 92 thousand.

According to the IOM research in 2014 - 2015, the number of internal labour migrants in Ukraine exceeds 1.6 million or 70% of general population labour mobility during the research period, and reaches 9% of the economically active population. The main internal migrant-sending regions are Western (48%) and Northern (23%) parts of Ukraine, the rest are from Eastern, Southern and Central parts (23%) (Mihratsiia, 2016, p. 31, 36). Recently growing out-migration could be traced in Donbas and Luhansk oblasts as of 2019.² The most attractive destinations for internal labour migrants are big cities such as: Kyiv, Lviv, Kharkiv, Dnipro and Odessa. Internal migration in Ukraine mainly depends on economic factors, such as the economic attractiveness of a region and a stable income gap between regions. The highest level of outflow of migrants is from regions with a lower level of economic development. Other non-economic factors that determine interregional migration are attractive living conditions, developed infrastructure and social security (Mihratsiia, 2016, p. 37).

The mass influx of IDPs started in 2014 and was mounting until 2016 reaching 1.6 million people in 2016 and slightly dropped by 2019 to 1.4 million (Mihratsiia, 2019, p.6). Most of them are located in the part of Donetsk region controlled by Ukraine – 0.5 million, and Luhansk region – 300 thousand and Kyiv and Kyiv region – 200 thousand together. Numerous groups of IDP are also in Kharkiv, Dnipropetrovsk, Zaporozhye regions (Ibid.).

² https://ukrstat.org/uk/operativ/operativ2019/ds/mr/mr_u/mr1219_u.html

Since the mid-1990s migration-related issues have been addressed in the numerous works based on qualitative large-scale survey methods and ethnographic methodology (Frejka, Okólski, Sword, 1999). The majority of research addressed labour migration and was focused on the international dimension (Pirozhkov, Malynovska, Marchenko, 1997). A major research was based on 440 in-depth interviews in migrant households in the cities of Kyiv, Chernivtsi and in a village close to Lviv. The research concluded that migration served as a survival strategy in the years of economic crisis and transition (Vollmer, Malynovska, 2016, p. 27). The same approach was used in the work focused on changes in structure, character and destination of migrations (Pirozhkov, Malinovskaya, Homra, 2003). Meanwhile recent survey-based research conducted by Polish scholars on Ukrainian migrants in Poland claims that “more and more migrants declare that they came to Poland in search for better incomes, and not due to lack of jobs in Ukraine” (Górny A. et al, 2019, p. 4).

In 2011 Donetsk Institute of Social Research and Political Analysis conducted the all-Ukrainian survey within the project “Migration potential of Ukraine in the context of obtaining a visa-free regime with the EU” funded by the European programs of the International Foundation “Vidrodzennya” (Renewal) affiliated with the Open Society Foundations.³ According to the study, one of the main drivers behind the desire of Ukrainians to migrate is the low income (80%) and the feeling of hopelessness in their home country (36%). The majority considers the lack of sufficient material resources to be the main deterrent to going abroad. Almost half of the respondents (46%) called it a significant obstacle for migration. The second most important barrier on the way for Ukrainians to leave for EU countries for long-term or permanent residence is the complexity of the visa procedure (28%) (Kipen, 2011, p 34). At the same time only 40% of respondents expressed their willingness to visit Schengen countries in the near future. In terms of migration potential, 23% are intended to go to the EU for temporary work and 10% for permanent residence (Ibid., p. 33).

The EU-funded project conducted in 2010 - 2015 investigated the impact of perceptions of human rights and democracy on migration aspirations and decisions.⁴ UMAGINE studied migration-related perceptions among people aged 18-39 in four countries of origin and transit: Morocco, Senegal, Turkey and Ukraine. The geographical focus in Ukraine was on:⁵

- Research Area with Immigration History: Solomyansky Rayon in Kyiv City;
- Research Area with Low emigration: Znamyanska Rayon in Kirovogradska Oblast;
- Research Area with specific Human Rights situation : Novovodolaz'ka rayon in Kharkivska Oblast;
- Research Area with High Emigration: Zbarazh Rayon in Ternopil'ska Oblast.

There has been very little research on internal migration in Ukraine so far. Some of the rare studies were based on statistical data (Kupets, 2012; Pozniak, 2013) as well as an analytical survey of current state of affairs (Malynovska, 2015). Recently some research on internal migrants based on ethnographic methodology emerged, aiming at understanding cultural adaptation of migrants from rural areas in Kyiv and Vinnitsa (Polek, 2017) and migration drivers, regarded as economic, non-economic and additional (Polek, 2015).

³ The national sample of 3002 people is three-stage, targeted, stratified. Possible sampling error $\pm 1.8\%$.

⁴ <http://eumagine.org/default.aspx>

⁵ http://eumagine.org/pages/eumagine_country_details.aspx?cid=4

According to the aforementioned research, among the main drivers behind the internal migration should be mentioned unprofitable agricultural production, unemployment (economic factors), low quality of education and medical care, poor development of the transport system, cultural sphere, leisure and recreation facilities (non-economic factors). Additional motives include the desire to conform to the image of a successful person, imposed by the media, the general level of migration among young people in the village and personal motives and ambitions (Polek, 2015, p. 232).

Picture: [Diana Vyshniakova/Unsplash.com](https://www.unsplash.com/photo-1517466772032-1c84c849796b)

2. The context for analysis driving to migration in the case study

2.1 Environmental conditions

Country-level environment characteristics

Ukraine has a total area of 603 550 km².⁶ It encompasses four agro-climatological zones: the humid zone (35%) in the northwest; the warm zone (25%) in the eastern and central Ukraine; the semi-arid zone (25%) in the far east (Donbas); the arid zone (15%) in the south including Crimean peninsula. The average annual precipitation over the country is 565 mm (FAO AQUASTAT, 2015, p. 3).

The country can be divided into seven major river basins: Dnipro - 65%; Dniester – 12%; Danube - 7%; coastal basin – 7%; Donets – 4%; Southern Bug – 3%; Western Bug – 2%. The total RSWR is estimated at 170 280 million m³/year. Internal renewable groundwater resources are estimated at 22 000 million m³/year (FAO AQUASTAT, 2015, p. 4-5). As of 2017 the cultivated area (arable land plus permanent crops) is estimated at 33.7 million ha or 55.8% of total country area and 1.1% of cultivated land irrigated.⁷

The most migrant sending areas as of 2019 are Donetsk oblast (-7.68 thousand people), Luhanska oblast (-4.94 thousand people), Kirovohradska oblast (-3.34 thousand people), Vinnytska oblast (-2.72 thousand people), Rivnenska oblast (2.47 thousand people).⁸ As far as Donetsk and Luhanska oblast are concerned, deterioration of the socio-economic conditions due to partial occupation by Russian proxies, including regional cities, are the main reasons for migration and environmental factors are rather irrelevant there. Instead, we would focus on the other main migrant-sending regions.

The other regions the bottom of the ranking, namely Vinnytska and Rivnenska oblasts have Low Middle RHD and Kirovohradska oblast has Low RHD.⁹ The largest population outflow in these regions is from the rural areas: Kirovohradska oblast (-2.66 thousand people), Vinnytska oblast (-3.54 thousand people), Rivnenska oblast (-1.64 thousand people).¹⁰ Environmental characteristics and agricultural production in three most migrant-sending areas are presented in Table 2.

⁶ Since 2014 7% of Ukrainian territory, including Crimea and some parts of Donbas, has been occupied by Russia and its proxies.

⁷ <http://www.fao.org/aquastat/statistics/query/results.html>

⁸ https://ukrstat.org/uk/operativ/operativ2019/ds/mr/mr_u/mr1219_u.html

⁹ Excluding the temporarily occupied territories of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea and the city of Sevastopol and parts of Luhansk and Donetsk regions. See: <https://www.minregion.gov.ua/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/Zaklyuch-zvit-Indeks-lyudskogo-rozvitku.pdf> P. 79.

¹⁰ http://www.ukrstat.gov.ua/operativ/operativ2020/ds/mr/mr_tm_r_2019.xlsx

Table 2. Local-level environmental characteristic of three most migrant-sending areas.

Source: State Statistic Service of Ukraine, Regional State Administrations.

	Climate	Hydrology	Soil	Agricultural production per capita in UAH as of 2019 ¹¹
Vinnyska oblast	warm zone	Dnister and Southern Bug basins Precipitation 480-550 mm	Cultivated area 78.0%	36 814
Kirovohradska oblast	warm zone	Dnipro and Southern Bug basins Precipitation 499-582 mm	Cultivated area 84.9%	38 320
Rivnenska oblast	humid zone	Dnipro basin Precipitation 600-700 mm	Cultivated area 48.2%	14 503

Vinnitska and Kirovohradska oblasts are the leading agricultural producers in Ukraine, while the level of agricultural production in Rivenenska oblast is compatible with the country's median – 15881.¹²

Main environmental drivers

The major environmentally-related disaster in Ukraine had a technogenic nature, namely the Chernobyl Catastrophe in 1986. The accident at the Chernobyl nuclear power plant caused radioactive contamination of the large areas at the north and northeast parts of Ukraine and border areas of Belarus. The Soviet government evacuated about 115 thousand people from the most heavily contaminated areas in 1986, and another 220 thousand people were resettled in the following years.

Every year, erosion causes the loss of 300 to 600 million tons of soil in Ukraine. The area of degraded and unproductive arable land in Ukraine is more than 6.5 million ha, or 20% of the total arable land.

Environmental and climate risk profiles

There are some studies and projections on the risks environmental and climate changes pose to Ukraine. The climate impacts Ukraine is projected to be most vulnerable to are droughts, heat waves, increased temperature, precipitation as well as floods and mudflows. Seasonal floods and droughts are expected to primarily impact the agricultural and the human health sectors (USAID, 2020; Fillecia et al., 2014). Mudslides and floods are expected to affect both urban and rural areas. The agricultural sector, which makes up 69 % of Ukraine's land use, is especially impacted by rainstorms. Furthermore, at least 10 % of the country's housing stock are considered to not be able to withstand extreme weather events (USAID, 2020; Nikolayeva et al. 2012).

Besides mudslides, the change in rainfall patterns and temperatures is expected to cause heat waves, water scarcity and the loss of agriculturally valuable soil from erosion. The soil loss alone is estimated to already cost one third of the agricultural GDP per year (USAID, 2020; Nikolayeva et al. 2012).

¹¹ http://www.ukrstat.gov.ua/operativ/operativ2017/sg/pro_sg/pro_sg_2019.xlsx

¹² Agricultural production per capita in UAH as of 2019.

Not only will Ukraine run into problems in terms of water supply but also when it comes to water quality. Already, a quarter of the 4100 lakes and water reservoirs do not satisfy the EU quality standards for drinking water. The percentage is even higher in rural areas (USAID, 2020; Nikolayeva et al. 2012; Massey 2012). In Ukraine's urban areas, the population will be increasingly affected by heat stress and rising pollution levels. At present, 48 % of deaths are caused by heart failure. This number is expected to rise even more due to heat waves (USAID, 2020; UNECE 2013).

2.2 Demographic situation (drivers)

The total population of Ukraine is estimated at 41,743,935 (excluding the temporarily occupied territories of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea, and the city of Sevastopol) as of August 1, 2020³³ (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Distribution of resident population in Ukraine by major age groups in 2020.
Source: State Statistic Service of Ukraine

Current demographic situation in Ukraine is characterised by gradual decline in the number of people living in the country. Since 1991 actual population in Ukraine decreased by 10,000,000 persons.³⁴ Ongoing depopulation is significantly impacted by the permanent surplus of mortality over fertility in Ukraine, especially in the rural localities.

³³ The number of population (estimation) is calculated according to the available administrative data on the official birth and death registration including changes in registration of the residence, excluding the temporarily occupied territories of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea and the city of Sevastopol: http://database.ukrcensus.gov.ua/PXWEB2007/eng/news/op_popul_e.asp

³⁴ [http://database.ukrcensus.gov.ua/MULT/Dialog/varval.asp?ma=02_01&ti=2.1.%20Distribution%20of%20the%20actual%20population%20by%20area%20type%20\(0,1\)&path=../Database/Pasport/2/&lang=2&multilang=en](http://database.ukrcensus.gov.ua/MULT/Dialog/varval.asp?ma=02_01&ti=2.1.%20Distribution%20of%20the%20actual%20population%20by%20area%20type%20(0,1)&path=../Database/Pasport/2/&lang=2&multilang=en)

Table 3. Natural Increase Rate of Ukraine 1991 – 2019¹⁵.

Year	Urban Settlements	Rural Localities	Aggregated
1991	1,1	-4,6	-0,8
1992	-0,4	-5,1	-2,0
1993	-2,1	-6,5	-3,5
1994	-3,5	-7,2	-4,7
1995	-4,8	-8,0	-5,8
1996	-4,9	-8,5	-6,0
1997	-5,0	-8,7	-6,2
1998	-5,0	-8,2	-6,0
1999	-6,0	-9,2	-7,1
2000	-6,6	-9,6	-7,6
2001	-6,6	-9,9	-7,6
2002	-6,3	-10,1	-7,6
2003	-6,0	-10,5	-7,5
2004	-5,5	-10,3	-7,0
2005	-5,9	-11,1	-7,6
2006	-4,9	-9,5	-6,4
2007	-4,8	-9,4	-6,2
2008	-3,8	-8,3	-5,3
2009	-2,9	-7,0	-4,2
2010	-3,3	-6,7	-4,4
2011	-2,3	-5,6	-3,5
2012	-2,2	-5,1	-3,1
2013	-2,6	-5,4	-3,5
2014	-3,0	-5,9	-3,9
2015	-2,8	-6,7	-4,2
2016	-3,2	-6,8	-4,4
2017	-3,8	-7,4	-5,1
2018	-4,9	-8,3	-6,1
2019	-5,5	-8,5	-6,6

The median age of Ukrainian population has been gradually increasing over past decades that in general corresponds to the current demographic situation in EU member states. But compared to developed high-income countries, the main reason to it is the decline at birth rate as well as outmigration, not the increasing of life expectancy among elderly population (Kupets, 2014) (Table 4).

¹⁵[http://database.ukrcensus.gov.ua/MULT/Dialog/varval.asp?ma=000_0203&ti=0203.%20Formation%20of%20increase%20\(decrease\)%20of%20the%20number%20of%20population%20by%20area%20type%20\(0,1\)&path=../Database/Population/02/01/&lang=2&multilang=en](http://database.ukrcensus.gov.ua/MULT/Dialog/varval.asp?ma=000_0203&ti=0203.%20Formation%20of%20increase%20(decrease)%20of%20the%20number%20of%20population%20by%20area%20type%20(0,1)&path=../Database/Population/02/01/&lang=2&multilang=en)

Table 4. The average population age 1991 – 2019¹⁶

Year	Urban Settlements	Rural Localities	Aggregated
1991	33,6	39,6	35,1
1992	33,9	39,5	35,3
1993	34,2	39,2	35,5
1994	34,6	39,0	35,5
1995	35,0	38,9	36,0
1996	35,3	38,8	36,0
1997	35,8	38,8	36,6
1998	36,2	38,9	37,0
1999	36,6	39,0	37,3
2000	37,0	39,2	37,7
2001	37,4	39,3	38,0
2002	36,7	38,5	37,3
2003	38,0	39,7	38,5
2004	38,2	39,8	38,7
2005	38,4	39,9	38,8
2006	38,5	40,0	39,0
2007	38,6	40,0	39,0
2008	38,7	40,1	39,1
2009	38,8	40,1	39,2
2010	39,0	40,0	39,3
2011	39,1	40,1	39,3
2012	39,4	40,1	39,6
2013	39,5	40,1	39,7
2014	39,7	40,1	39,8
2015	39,9	40,2	40,0
2016	40,2	40,3	40,2
2017	40,5	40,4	40,5
2018	40,9	40,5	40,8
2019	41,6	40,3	41,4

According to the forecast by the UN Population Division, population of Ukraine will decrease to 35.2 million, and the share of people older than 60 years will be 34% by 2050.¹⁷ Olga Kupets argues that in Ukraine where “aging takes place against the backdrop of weak institutions, structural weaknesses and vulnerabilities of the economy, political instability and low level of trust among the population” this process is especially challenging (Kupets, 2014, p. 100) (Fig. 4).

¹⁶[http://database.ukrcensus.gov.ua/MULT/Dialog/varval.asp?ma=000_0208&ti=0208.%20Average%20and%20median%20age%20of%20population%20\(0,1\)&path=../Database/Population/02/02/&lang=2&multilang=en](http://database.ukrcensus.gov.ua/MULT/Dialog/varval.asp?ma=000_0208&ti=0208.%20Average%20and%20median%20age%20of%20population%20(0,1)&path=../Database/Population/02/02/&lang=2&multilang=en)

¹⁷ World Population Prospects – United Nations Population Division, <https://population.un.org/wpp/Download/Probabilistic/Population/>

Figure 4. Age dependency ratio in Ukraine 1990 – 2019.¹⁸

Source: The World Bank

Kupets points out that “compared with higher-income ageing countries, Ukraine has fewer financial resources for mitigating the negative impacts of population ageing on the labour market, the social protection and health systems” (Kupets, 2014, p. 100).

Demographic processes in Ukraine in the 20th century, especially during the Soviet period, made it predominantly an urban country (Petryshyn, 2016). According to Tina Polek, after the peak of industrialization in 1939, the urban population had doubled and amounted to 34%, and the rural population, respectively, rotated to 66%. The annual increase in the number of urban population led to the point of comparison with the rural population in the 1950s, and the number of urban residents continued to grow slowly and in 2014 amounted to 69% (Polek, 2017, p. 260).

Halyna Petryshyn reported that the specific feature of the urbanisation processes in Ukraine in 1950–1970s was the functioning of a large number of small cities. At the same period urban agglomerations around Kyiv, Kharkiv, Dnipropetrovsk (Dnipro), Stalino (Donetsk), Odessa, Lviv started to be formed. The next stage of urbanisation in 1980–1990s is characterised by the agglomerating phenomenon of urbanisation development (Petryshyn, 2016, p. 42).

The spatial distribution of the actual population in Ukraine hasn't changed significantly since 1991 and the urban population share only slightly increased, from 67,5% in 1991 to 69,5% in 2020.¹⁸ In 1991 – 2017 due to depopulation and migration processes settlement density decreased from 49 settlements per 1, 000 sq. km to 48 (Pirozhkov, S. et al, 2018, p. 148). In this case, the number of urban settlements increased by 5,4%¹⁹ with a decline in urban population density from 56 to 49 people per sq. km, and the total number of rural settlements per urban area decreased from 66 units in 1991 to 61,5 in 2020.²⁰

¹⁸ <https://databank.worldbank.org/reports.aspx?source=2&series=SP.POP.DPND&country=UKR>

¹⁹ [http://database.ukrcensus.gov.ua/MULT/Dialog/varval.asp?ma=02_01&ti=2.1.%20Distribution%20of%20the%20actual%20population%20by%20area%20type%20\(0,1\)&path=../Database/Pasport/2/&lang=2&multilang=en](http://database.ukrcensus.gov.ua/MULT/Dialog/varval.asp?ma=02_01&ti=2.1.%20Distribution%20of%20the%20actual%20population%20by%20area%20type%20(0,1)&path=../Database/Pasport/2/&lang=2&multilang=en)

²⁰ [http://database.ukrcensus.gov.ua/MULT/Dialog/varval.asp?ma=000_0101&ti=0101.%20Number%20of%20administrative-territory%20divisions%20\(0,1\)&path=../Database/Population/01/&lang=2&multilang=en](http://database.ukrcensus.gov.ua/MULT/Dialog/varval.asp?ma=000_0101&ti=0101.%20Number%20of%20administrative-territory%20divisions%20(0,1)&path=../Database/Population/01/&lang=2&multilang=en)

The demographic processes in Ukraine during the last three decades resulted in increasing concentration of population in economic centres and areas with advanced economic activity and depopulation of remote rural areas and small towns due to outflow of young and economically active population (Pirozhkov, S. et al, 2018, p. 148).

According to Ukrainian legislation, cities are settlements with no less than 10, 000 residents and 2/3 of the population employed outside the agricultural sector. Currently, about 1/5 of Ukrainian cities do not meet the specified characteristics. In addition, the population of urban-type settlements with over 2,000 residents and 2/3 of them employed outside the agricultural sector is regarded as urban and consequently reported as urban population in the official statistics (Ibid., 151).

2.3 Sociocultural context

National and regional profiles (Social development)

As it was already mentioned in the report, low income, poor quality of education and medical care, insufficient development of the transport system, cultural sphere, leisure and recreation facilities are regarded the main migration drivers in Ukraine, especially from the rural areas.

In 2018, Ukraine was ranked 88 among 189 countries on UN’s Human Development Index (HDI), estimated as 0,750²¹ that brings it to a high human development category.

Figure 5. Trends in Ukraine’s HDI component indices 1990 – 2018²²

²¹ Ibid.

²² [https://www.ua.undp.org/content/dam/ukraine/docs/Annual%20Reports/Ukraine-\(eng\)-HDR-2019.pdf](https://www.ua.undp.org/content/dam/ukraine/docs/Annual%20Reports/Ukraine-(eng)-HDR-2019.pdf)

Since 1990 Ukraine has demonstrated positive dynamics of HDI. Its value increased from 0,705 to 0,750, or 6,3%. Also Ukraine's life expectancy at birth increased by 2,1 years, mean years of schooling increased by 2,2 years and expected years of schooling increased by 2,7 years. At the same period Ukraine's GNI per capita decreased by about 25,6%. However, since 2003 these indicators have been constantly increasing. Meanwhile the coefficient of human inequality that indicates inequalities in health, education and income is 6,5%, and Inequality-adjusted HDI (IHDI) falls to 0,701 (Ibid.).

The Multidimensional Poverty Index identifies multiple overlapping deprivations suffered by individuals in 3 dimensions: health, education and standard of living.²³ In Ukraine as of 2012 0,2 % of the population (106 thousand people) are multidimensionally poor while an additional 0,4 % are classified as vulnerable to multidimensional poverty (185 thousand people). The breadth of deprivation (intensity) in Ukraine, which is the average deprivation score experienced by people in multidimensional poverty, is 34,5%.²⁴

The Regional Human Development Index (RHDI) in Ukraine is calculated according to the methodology of the Institute of Demography and Social Research of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine. RHDI is constructed from 33 indicators that correspond to 6 dimensions:

population reproduction; social status; comfortable life; welfare; decent work; education. RHDI forms a composed indicator for a certain region of Ukraine (Metodyka, 2012). Since 2016 RHDI has been constructed from 8 indicators, corresponding to 3 dimensions: long and healthy life; prosperity and decent working conditions; education (Libanova, 2017, p. 67-74).

According to the RHDI calculations, Kyiv city constantly tops the rating. The other Ukrainian regions have been divided into three categories as of 2016 (Ibid., p. 79):²⁵

- High RHDI: Lviv region, Kharkiv region; Chernintsi region;
- Upper middle RHDI: Zakarpattia region, Zaporizhia region, Kyiv region;
- Middle RHDI: Dnipropetrovsk region, Ivano-Frankivsk region, Mykolaiv region, Odesa region, Poltava region, Ternopil region, Chernyhiiv region;
- Low middle RHDI: Vinnytsia region, Volyn region, Rivne region, Khmelnytsky region, Cherkasy region;
- Low RHDI: Zhytomyr region, Kirovohrad region, Sumy region, Kherson region

²³ A deprivation score of 33.3 % (one-third of the weighted indicators) is used to distinguish between the poor and nonpoor. If the deprivation score is 33.3 % or greater, the household (and everyone in it) is classified as multidimensionally poor.

²⁴ [https://www.ua.undp.org/content/dam/ukraine/docs/Annual%20Reports/Ukraine-\(eng\)-HDR-2019.pdf](https://www.ua.undp.org/content/dam/ukraine/docs/Annual%20Reports/Ukraine-(eng)-HDR-2019.pdf)

²⁵ Excluding the temporarily occupied territories of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea and the city of Sevastopol and parts of Luhansk and Donetsk regions. See:

<https://www.minregion.gov.ua/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/Zaklyuch-zvit-Indeks-lyudskogo-rozvitku.pdf> P. 79.

Table 5. Ranks of regions according to the composed assessment of regional human development index (RHDI) 2010 – 2015. (Libanova, 2017, p. 78)

	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
Kyiv	1	1	1	1	1	1
Lviv region	5	7	5	3	4	3
Kyiv region	6	2	8	8	8	7
Kharkiv region	4	4	2	2	2	2
Chernivtsi region	3	3	3	5	3	4
Ivano-Frankivsk region	14	13	14	17	19	10
Ternopil region	10	11	12	16	10	12
Zakarpattia region	2	5	4	4	5	5
Rivne region	15	15	16	14	18	19
Volyn region	16	20	15	11	11	16
Odesa region	11	8	9	10	9	8
Khmelnysky region	18	19	20	19	15	18
Dnipropetrivsk region	9	12	13	13	14	14
Poltava region	8	9	7	9	7	9
Vinnysia region	17	18	17	18	17	17
Zaporizhia region	12	10	6	6	6	6
Mykolaiv region	13	14	11	7	12	11
Sumy region	19	16	19	22	20	20
Cherkasy region	7	6	10	12	13	15
Zhytomyr region	21	23	23	23	23	21
Kherson	22	21	21	20	22	22
Chernyiv region	20	17	18	16	16	13
Kirovohrad region	23	22	22	21	21	23

Figure 6. Ukraine RHDI 2019. (Rozrahunok, 2019).²⁶

²⁶ Excluding the temporarily occupied territories of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea and the city of Sevastopol and parts of Luhansk and Donetsk regions. See: <https://www.minregion.gov.ua/wp-content/>

Family ties and other networks

Family structure

Analysis of family distribution by types conducted by the Institute of Demography and Social Research of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine indicates that a nuclear family consisting of a married couple with or without children is the prevailing family type in Ukraine: it accounted for 56,2% of all family households at the time of the last population census in 2001 (Libanova et al, 2009, p. 21). For the same period, the percentage of extended families consisting of two or more married couples decreased in urban areas, while slightly grew in the rural areas. Therefore, extended multigenerational families are not typical for Ukraine, especially in urban areas (Ibid., p. 22).

The ties between the members of immediate family in Ukraine are traditionally quite strong, that in turn facilitates the development of informal family networks in the country and beyond (Fedyuk, 2012). As it has been argued during the expert focus group, family connections have impact on migration's destination, i.e. family members present in the hosting countries serve as a gatekeepers for the newcomers and could help a job and accommodation in the host countries.²⁷

Diaspora

Today there are from 8,2 million (as indicated by the foreign countries' censuses) to 20 million (according to various estimates) people of Ukrainian origin living abroad (Malynovska, 2016, p. 17). Ukrainian diasporas are present in great numbers in CIS countries, Europe and Americas. It is segmented on duration of stay, legal and social status, skills, ethnic and religious identity, migration motives. We could distinguish between old or historical diasporas, shaped by the first three waves of migrations from the territory of the present-day Ukraine in the late XIX – 1991, and new diasporas established by migrants from independent Ukraine (Yas, no date). Ukrainian diasporas traditionally maintain close relations with their country of origin and contribute to its development in different ways (Lapshyna, 2019). Iryna Lapshyna claims that "main challenges to diaspora engagement with affairs in Ukraine have been described as a lack of commitment by the origin country, notably its authorities, mistrust between governments and some diaspora organisations and, in some cases, a lack of unity among diaspora members." (Ibid., p. 69). The Ukrainian diaspora worldwide is represented by the Ukrainian World Congress, an international coordination assembly of all Ukrainian public organisations in diaspora. The Congress has member organisations in 33 countries and ties with Ukrainians in 14 additional countries.²⁸

Ties with the Ukrainian diaspora are coordinated by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs. MFA also supports the activity of the National Commission for Matters Concerning Ukrainians Abroad established under the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine that includes representatives from all relevant government agencies and representatives of the diaspora.

Religious networks

Today Ukraine is a multi-faith society, where religion plays an important role in the social interactions and identity construction. According to the survey conducted by the Ukrainian Centre for Economic and Political Studies named after Olexander Razumkov in 2019, the number of those who recognize themselves believers is currently 66%, while the number of those who varies between faith and unbelief is 12,2%, the number of unbelievers is 5,4%, the number of convinced atheists is 4%, the number of those indifferent to matters of faith 6,5%, the number of those who did not decide on matters of faith is 5,9%. (Relihiia, 2020, p. 11). Jose Casanova claims that the situation in Ukraine is characterised by multi-religious denominationalism similar to that of the USA (Casanova, 2013).

²⁷ Expert focus-group on migration organised by Centre for Applied Anthropology in Kyiv on January 12, 2021.

²⁸ <http://ukrainianworldcongress.org/info/index.html>

Figure 7. Religious composition of Ukrainian society in 2019 (Relihiia, 2020, p. 14)

In the West, 36% of the population recognized themselves as Greek Catholics. In the South and East, most respondents associated themselves with the Orthodox Church (69% and 66%, respectively) (Ibid.).

In December 2018, the Ukrainian Orthodox Church (Kyiv Patriarchate) merged with the Ukrainian Autocephalous Church giving birth to the Orthodox Church of Ukraine (OCU), which in January 2019 received from the Ecumenical Patriarchate Tomos (canonical decree) on autocephaly. However, in May 2019 the Honorary Patriarch of OCU Filaret withdrew his signature on the decision to establish the OCU and announced the restoration of the Kyiv Patriarchate. By that time, among the number of the Orthodox believers, 20% referred to the OCU, 12% to the Kyiv Patriarchate and 16% to Moscow Patriarchate. At the same time 47% respondents recognized themselves "just Orthodox" (Ibid., p. 15).

Muslims represent one of the major religious minorities in Ukraine. Government agencies and independent think tanks estimate the Muslim population at 500,000. Some Muslim leaders put the number at two million. According to government figures, up to 300,000 of these are Crimean Tatars.²⁹

The ethnic history of Islam in Ukraine goes back to the Crimean Tatar and Lipka Tatar population in the early modern period. The later development of Muslim minorities in Ukraine is connected to the population mobility in the days of Russian Empire and Soviet Union.

²⁹http://2001.ukrcensus.gov.ua/results/nationality_population/nationality_popul1/select_5/?botton=cens_db&box=5.1W&k_t=01&p=125&rZ=1_1&rZ_b=2_1%2520%2520%2520%2520%2520&n_page=6

Along with Crimean Tatars the other major ethnic groups of Muslim population in Ukraine are (as of 2001, when the last All-Ukrainian Population Census took place):

- Volga Tatars – 73300
- Azeri – 45176
- Uzbek – 12 353
- Meskheti Turks – 10000³⁰
- Kazakh - 5500
- Turkmen – 3700

Among the other Muslim ethnic groups of migrant origin in Ukraine we could mention natives of North Caucasus, Turkey, MENA, Afghanistan, Pakistan, Bangladesh, and Nigeria; these groups include a number of fresh as well as naturalized migrants. Currently, migration begins to play more significant role in Muslim population dynamics in Ukraine. Ukraine also attracts a number of those who stay in Ukraine for the purpose of study. Some of them use Ukraine as a hub for further westward migration.

Table 6. Number of foreign students from Muslim-majority countries in Ukraine

Source: State Migration Service of Ukraine

Morocco	Turkmenistan	Turkey	Nigeria	Egypt	Jordan	Israel (including Palestine)	Iran
6 964	4 192	4 062	3 600	3 209	2 605	2 230	1 807

The religious organisations play an important role in the life of the Ukrainian migrant communities, especially in the US. The largest in the United States is the Ukrainian Catholic Church, whose four dioceses number more than 400,000 people. The second largest place is the Ukrainian Orthodox Church, which has more than 200,000 believers in more than a hundred Orthodox parishes. There is an annual trend towards an increase in the number of Orthodox parishioners, which can be explained by the increase in immigrants from Eastern and Central Ukraine over the past 10 years. The number of Ukrainian Evangelical Baptists and Pentecostal Christians is growing rapidly. In the last decade almost 50,000 Ukrainians have settled on the Pacific coast, most of them belonging to the Baptist and Pentecostal denominations (Kukhareno, 2015).

Cultural networks

Contemporary cultural networks in Ukraine are a kind of collaboration network that enables an environment for cooperation in the cultural sphere in Ukraine and abroad. According to the research based on evaluation of 85 European/global cultural networks, Ukraine has been represented in 31% of the networks as of 2000.³¹ Country report issued under the Preparatory Action “Culture in the EU’s External Relations” in 2014 indicated that in Ukraine, external cultural policy was fragmented between a variety of non-state initiatives, including several philanthropic foundations created by local ‘oligarchs’ as well as dynamic cities (Ukraine, 2016, p. 3), and “Ukraine’s external cultural policy-making system has been highly centralised and pyramidal, with the Presidential apparatus playing a leading role, while the responsible ministries act as bureaucratic implementing agencies” (Ibid., p. 4).

³⁰ Since 2014 several thousands of Meshketi Turks escaped from the volatile Donbas region to Turkey.

³¹ In the evaluation of 85 membership lists, the countries in which at least one member of the respective network is located were identified. See: <https://eipcp.net/policies/nwcee/en/ecn-en1.pdf> P.11.

Currently development of Ukrainian cultural networks is supported by Ukrainian Cultural Foundation, EU “Creative Europe” programme and other institutions and initiatives. These projects and other activities aim at promoting the formation of new Ukrainian and international networks in the cultural and arts sectors in order to enhance the role of culture in the development of society and internationalisation of Ukrainian culture.³²

2.4 Return migration

The return migration has a positive impact on domestic economic development in terms of transfer of accumulated financial capital, human capital (experience, skills, knowledge, business practices, ideas, etc.), and social capital (contacts, networks) (Mihratsiia, 2016, p. 47).

The report produced within the Research and Policy Dialogue Initiative on Migration and Remittances in Ukraine project, implemented by the International Organisation for Migration (IOM), Mission in Ukraine in 2014 – 2016 indicates that 144,400 international long-term migrant workers or 39% of the total current long-term migrant workers population have returned to Ukraine for permanent stay (Ibid., p.11). According to the migrant survey, overall, 60% of long-term labour migrants have an intention to return permanently to Ukraine, 21% want to stay and further 19% remain undecided (Ibid., p. 48). These numbers are similar to those expected from EU countries: 65%, 21% and 14% respectively (Ibid.).

According to the IOM report, in terms of age, those in the 18-29 age group are much more likely to stay abroad (30%), than in the 45-65 age group (16%). In terms of gender, women are less likely to return permanently (54% as compared to 63% of male migrant workers), as well as those migrant workers originating from urban areas (51% compared to 69% from rural areas) (Ibid.). The vast majority of Ukrainian migrant workers want to return to their place of origin (Ibid.). According to the National Bank of Ukraine estimations, because of the COVID-19 pandemic and lockdown in the migrant receiving countries about 10% of Ukrainian labour migrants or 300,000 have returned to Ukraine in 2020.³³ At the same time, Ukrainian experts on migration suggested, that the main wave of return migration took place in March-April 2020, and that currently most of the migrants have returned to the host countries.³⁴

At present the State Employment Service of Ukraine is creating business development centres and modernising one-off unemployment benefits for entrepreneurship, but the effectiveness of such policies is not clear yet (Ukraintsi, 2017).

2.5 Education

The Ukrainian educational system encompasses five levels:

- Preschool;
- Elementary school,
- Lower secondary school;
- Upper secondary level:
- Upper Secondary Special School (Licei),
- Upper Secondary Special School (Gimnazia),
- Upper Secondary School (Starsha Serednia Shkola),
- Vocational School (Profesijno-Tecnichne Uchylshche).

³² See: https://ucf.in.ua/en/m_lots/5dbb66e3b1ce513f252ad382

³³ https://bank.gov.ua/admin_uploads/article/IR_2020-Q2.pdf?v=4

³⁴ Expert focus-group on migration organised by Centre for Applied Anthropology in Kyiv on January 12, 2021.

- Higher education level:
- First level of accreditation (Vocational Secondary School (Technikum),
- Second level of accreditation (College),
- Third level of accreditation (Institutes, Universities, Conservatories, Academies)
- Forth level of accreditation (Institutes, Universities, Conservatories, Academies).

As of 2018 expected years of schooling were 15,2 (female) and 14,1 (male); mean years of schooling - 11,3 (female), 11,3 (male) (Human Development Report, 2019). Inequality of education is estimated at 3,6%.

As of 2019 the net coverage of preschool educational institutions in Ukraine for children aged three to five years as a percentage to the total number of children aged is 76,4% (Rozrahunok, 2019). The lack of vacancies in preschool institutions could be observed in all regions of Ukraine without exception. It is relevant not only for urban settlements, where preschools are overcrowded, but this problem has also become widespread in rural areas (Libanova, 2017, p. 58).

To date, the number of graduates of higher educational institutions of I-IV level of accreditation as a percentage to the total population aged 25-70 years is 1,4% (Rozrahunok, 2019). Regional differences in the educational and qualification level of an adult population are driven by the economic development of the regions, their urbanisation, development of local labour markets, since highly skilled professionals have much more opportunities to find a high-paying job in the industrialised centres regions of Ukraine. On the other hand, such concentration of skilled labour force in these regions begins to act as an independent factor, which forms the appropriate image of the region, ensuring their economic, social and investment attractiveness (Libanova, 2017, p. 60).

Risks and challenges

According to the World Bank report on the labour force mobility impact on economics in Ukraine, internal migration routes do not always lead from the economically depressed regions to the more developed, but depend on other factors: higher level of expenditures on the social sphere, more developed social infrastructure and other facilities typical for large cities (In search of opportunities, 2012). Therefore, disproportional regional social development, especially with regard to the difference in HDI level in rural and urban areas, is the most important driver of internal migration, that could lead to further socio-economic decline and depopulation of the migrant sending rural areas.

IOM Migration Governance Snapshot indicated that Ukraine still doesn't have a comprehensive program of reintegration of returning migrants. The "Strategy of State Migration Policy" declares creating conditions for the return of Ukrainian emigrants as a policy goal in the State but not yet elaborated in the program documents, while the Law "On External Labor Migration" briefly mentions creation of favourable conditions for return to Ukraine and reintegration of academic and cultural figures, qualified specialists and workers required by the national economy (Ukraine Profile, 2019, p. 6).³⁵

The issues of double taxation and the requirement to declare the source of income of migrant workers remain unresolved (Ukraintsi, 2017). Thus, migrant workers today must declare in Ukraine the income received abroad, filing an annual tax return, and make deductions from them - 18% personal income tax (PIT) and 1.5% military tax. Currently the State Tax Service of Ukraine (STSU) wants more migrant workers to pay taxes. According to STSU remittances sent to Ukraine is about \$ 12 billion a year, while tax returns, which are submitted annually to STSU, reflect only 11 billion UAH (approximately 400 million \$), or about 30 times less. STSU wants to restrict the rules in order to make declarations obligatory for all labour migrants.

³⁵ See: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/761-19> <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/482-2017-%D1%80#Text>

2.6 Economic context

National and regional profiles (Economic development)

According to the World Bank, Ukraine as an emerging free market economy belongs to lower middle-income countries. In 2019 GNI per capita was 3,370 US\$, that is still 25,6% less than back in 1990.³⁶ The most important drivers of the Ukrainian Economy are the industrial sector, trade and agricultural sector. Industrial sector includes about 20 major industries: power generating, fuel, ferrous and non-ferrous metallurgy, chemical and petrochemical and gas, machine-building and metal-working, forest, wood-working and wood pulp and paper, construction materials, light, and food. Ukraine possesses 30% of the world's richest black soil and its agricultural industry has a huge potential. As of 2018 Ukraine considered the world's largest producer of sunflower seed, the 3rd largest world producer of potato, 5th largest world producer of maize, 8th largest world producer of wheat, and has leading positions in production of other agricultural goods.³⁷

Ukraine has experienced de-industrialization and the share of industry in Ukraine's economy has declined twice since 1991, from around 50% of Gross Value Added (GVA) to 24,2 in 2019.

Figure 8. Share of Economy Sectors of CVA in Ukraine as of 2019³⁸

As of August 2020 the estimated labour force in Ukraine (aged 15-70) as of 2020 is 17,33 million (66% of population) and unemployment rate 9,9%.³⁹ The special distribution of unemployment as of June 2020 was 8,7% in urban areas and 10,1% in rural areas.⁴⁰

According to the survey by Center for Economic Strategy, the number of forced part-time employment and unpaid leave temporarily increased to 3,1 million or 17% of the labor force in 2020 during the lockdown caused by Covid 19 pandemic (Mykhailyshyna, 2020). The sectoral distribution of employment dynamics looks as follows (see Table 7).

³⁶ <https://data.worldbank.org/country/ukraine?view=chart>

³⁷ http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#rankings/countries_by_commodity

³⁸ http://www.ukrstat.gov.ua/operativ/infografika/2020/soc_ek_r_Ukr/soc_ek_r_Ukr_o8_2020.pdf

³⁹ Ibid.

⁴⁰ Data exclude the temporarily occupied territory of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea, the city of Sevastopol and a part of temporarily occupied territories in Donetsk and Luhansk. See: regions http://www.ukrstat.gov.ua/operativ/operativ2017/rp/leas/leas_u/arch_nzn_smpvg_u.htm

Table 7. Sectoral distribution of employment in 2012 – 2019 (1000, aged 15-70)⁴¹

	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Total	19 261,4	19 314,2	18 073,3	16 443,2	16 276,9	16 156,4	16 360,9	16 578,3
Agriculture	3 308,5	3 389,0	3 091,4	2 870,6	2 866,5	2 860,7	2 937,0	3 010,4
Industry	3 236,7	3 170,0	2 898,2	2 573,9	2 494,8	2 440,6	2 426,0	2 461,5
Construction	836,4	841,1	746,4	642,1	644,5	644,3	665,3	699,0
Trade	4 160,2	4 269,5	3 965,7	3 510,7	3 516,2	3 525,8	3 654,7	3 801,3
Transport and logistic	1 150,9	1 163,6	1 113,4	998,0	997,2	991,6	995,1	999,0
Hotels and restaurants	326,7	328,9	309,1	277,3	276,7	276,3	283,0	304,0
IT	297,9	299,9	284,8	272,9	275,2	274,1	280,3	289,2
Finances	315,8	306,2	286,8	243,6	225,6	215,9	214,0	211,6
Real Estate	322,2	314,3	286,1	268,3	255,5	252,3	259,4	259,7
Science and technology	504,1	493,6	456,0	422,9	428,1	415,8	437,9	421,6
Administrative services	343,9	343,3	334,3	298,6	304,3	297,9	304,3	317,9
Public service, defence and social security	1 003,6	962,3	959,5	974,5	973,1	979,7	939,3	870,5
Education	1 633,2	1 611,2	1 587,7	1 496,5	1 441,4	1 423,4	1 416,5	1 388,7
Health and social service	1 181,4	1 171,8	1 150,5	1 040,7	1 030,4	1 013,6	995,4	974,2
Art, sport and leisure	225,6	226,5	221,2	207,9	1 030,4	199,8	196,9	197,6
Other	414	423,0	382,2	344,7	345,8	344,6	355,2	372,1

It should be noted that employment in the agricultural sector, which is prevalent in the migrant-sending areas, as a percentage of the employed adult population has not changed much in recent times compared to the industrial sector employment that has dropped more significantly.

Since 2010 the average monthly nominal wage increased from 204 EUR in 2010 to 336 EUR in 2020.⁴² At the same time, in euro equivalent it increased from 204 EUR in 2010 to 336 EUR in 2020.

Table 8. Sectoral distribution of average wage and wage arrears as of September 2020 ⁴³

	2012	Arrears (million EUR)
Minimum	144,4	
Total		3,20
Total Average	350	
Agriculture	292	1,65
Industry	395	77,3
Construction	306	1,30
Trade	350	0,98
Transport and logistic	382	9,54
Hotels and restaurants	190	0,39
IT	606	0,31
Finances	602	0,33
Real Estate	283	1,85
Science and technology	475	7,98
Administrative services	307	0,49
Public service, defence and social security	514	0,17
Education	251	0,56
Health and social service	259	1,7
Art, sport and leisure	293	0,03

⁴¹ Excluding the temporarily occupied territories of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea and the city of Sevastopol (2012-2019) and parts of Luhansk and Donetsk regions since 2015. See: http://www.ukrstat.gov.ua/operativ/operativ2014/rp/zn_ed/zn_ed_u/zn_ed_2013_u.htm

⁴² Ibid.

⁴³ Ibid.

Ukraine is characterised by moderately uneven socio-economic development of the regions, while 2/3 regions belong to the middle group (ranked 6-20). These disproportions are one of the key drivers of internal migration. The rank is constructed from several indicators: economic efficiency, investment development and foreign economic cooperation, financial self-sufficiency, labour market efficiency, infrastructure development, renewable energy and energy efficiency. As the following table shows, regional socio-economic development is quite volatile, and cells marked red indicate fluctuations.

Table 9. Regional socio-economic development ranks in 2015 – 2020 ⁴⁴

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Kyiv	1	1	1	1	1	1
Lviv region	9	13	9	11	8	8
Kyiv region	6	3	14	8	5	2
Kharkiv region	2	2	2	2	6	12
Chernivtsi region	3	5	5	6	7	23
Ivano-Frankivsk region	4	12	8	16	14	19
Ternopil region	15	20	6	7	10	22
Zakarpattia region	8	16	4	13	20	21
Rivne region	11	6	16	3	4	4
Volyn region	12	9	15	10	18	16
Odesa region	18	15	9	21	13	13
Khmelnysky region	13	8	20	11	17	6
Dnipropetrivsk region	5	10	4	5	3	3
Poltava region	14	17	15	10	15	14
Vinnitsia region	7	4	7	4	2	11
Zaporizhia region	17	14	20	20	23	17
Mykolaiv region	22	19	23	21	12	17
Sumy region	19	23	19	17	21	20
Cherkasy region	10	7	16	9	11	15
Zhytomyr region	16	11	12	13	16	10
Kherson	20	21	18	18	19	18
Chernyhiv region	23	22	22	23	22	9
Kirovohrad region	21	18	17	15	9	5
Luhansk region	24	25	25	25	24	24
Donetsk region	25	24	24	24	25	25

Kyiv's profile

We have chosen Kyiv as the research area due to several reasons. The statistics of population mobility in Ukraine indicate that statistically recorded internal migration numbers are about 10 times more than registered external migration cases. More than half of all relocations usually took place inside regions and only about a third are interregional (Malynovska, 2015, p. 3). Kyiv, the capital of Ukraine is the most attractive place for internal migrants in terms of residential as well as circular and pendulum migration.

⁴⁴ See: <https://www.minregion.gov.ua/napryamki-diyalnosti/regional-dev/derzhavna-rehional-na-polityka/monitorynh/monitorynh-monitorynh/rejtingova-otsinka-regioniv/>

Table 10. Population change and migration in Kyiv in 2005 - 2019 ⁴⁵

Year	Overall Population Size (1000s)	Natural Increase/Decrease	In-Migration (persons)
2005	2 666,4	-3 817	30 640
2006	2 693,2	-1 819	26 691
2007	2 718,1	-2 666	24 803
2008	2 740,2	1 898	23 400
2009	2 765,5	4 196	15 404
2010	2 785,1	3 457	10 611
2011	2 799,2	5 018	10 401
2012	2 814,3	6 047	24 718
2013	2 845,0	5 302	18 377
2014	2 868,7	4 829	14 443
2015	2 888,0	5 133	13 462
2016	2 906,6	5 903	13 288
2017	2 925,8	4 551	4 211
2018	2 934,5	2 355	13 942
2019	2 950,8	-634	17 175

Figure 9. Migration Rate in Kyiv in 2005 – 2019 (per 1000 people)

Kyiv city consistently demonstrates high indicators of socio-economic development and is at the top of the RHDH ranking. The high housing prices forces migrants to settle in the suburbs or closest to the capital settlements, which leads to an increase in the share of pendulum migrants. As for 2010 one third of the Kyiv region population or 50,5% of pendulum migrants worked in Kyiv (Kupets, 2012). By that time, the number of unregistered residential migrants working in Kyiv was 450,000 (including family members) and 225,000 pendulum migrants (including 50,000 students) (Pozniak, 2013, p. 63).

⁴⁵<http://www.Kyiv.ukrstat.gov.ua/p.php3?c=527&lang=1>

Table 11. Labour market in Kyiv 2005 - 2019 ⁴⁶

Year	Overall labour force aged 15-70 years, 1000s	% to overall population aged 15-70 years	Employed population aged 15-70 years, 1000s	% to overall population aged 15-70 years	Unemployed population aged 15-70 years, 1000s	% to overall labour force aged 15-70 years ILO methodology	Average job seeking time, month, ILO methodology
2005	1 412,6	66,2	1 352,0	63,3	60,6	4,3	8
2006	1 425,7	65,9	1 375,6	63,6	50,1	3,5	7
2007	1 450,0	66,5	1 405,3	64,4	45,0	3,1	6
2008	1 465,7	66,9	1 420,2	64,9	45,5	3,1	7
2009	1 477,5	67,5	1 381,0	63,1	96,5	6,5	6
2010	1 473,7	67,5	1 387,8	63,6	85,9	5,8	9
2011	1 483,5	68,2	1 401,0	64,4	82,5	5,6	9
2012	1 480,8	68,2	1 399,8	64,5	81,0	5,5	9
2013	1 490,6	68,4	1 413,1	64,9	77,5	5,2	10
2014	1 466,8	67,1	1 368,1	62,6	98,7	6,7	7
2015	1 460,4	66,7	1 357,8	62,0	102,6	7,0	11
2016	1 461,6	66,7	1 364,3	62,3	97,3	6,7	10
2017	1 457,9	66,4	1 356,8	61,8	101,1	6,9	10
2018	1 459,3	66,8	1 368,6	62,6	90,7	6,2	9
2019	1 464,6	67,0	1 379,9	63,1	84,7	5,8	7

Kyiv city consistently demonstrates high indicators of socio-economic development and is at the top of the RHDJ ranking. The high housing prices forces migrants to settle in the suburbs or closest to the capital settlements, which leads to an increase in the share of pendulum migrants. As for 2010 one third of the Kyiv region population or 50,5% of pendulum migrants worked in Kyiv (Kupets, 2012). By that time, the number of unregistered residential migrants working in Kyiv was 450,000 (including family members) and 225,000 pendulum migrants (including 50,000 students) (Pozniak, 2013, p. 63).

- high concentration and intensity of pendulum migrations within one and a half hours of accessibility by transport corridors;
- the specific structure of migration flows, due to the needs of the metropolitan labour market, where the industrial and information sectors of the economy predominate, mostly with the requirements of permanent employment, and, accordingly, a small share of temporary or seasonal labour migrants;
- dominance of movements in the direction of "city-city", "urban settlement-city" and, accordingly, their high share in the total volume of pendulum migrations;
- strong motivation of the permanent population of the metropolitan area to temporarily change the place of residence, mostly in the direction of the place of work, the centre of business, social or other activity;
- use of metropolitan areas to accommodate internal forced migrants;
- dependence of the intensity of migration in the direction of the centre-periphery on the features of spatial development of metropolises.

Kyiv metropolis is characterised as polycentric, with redistribution of the pendulum migration in favour of suburban settlements where high-tech enterprises of construction, light, food, chemical, perfume and cosmetics industries operate (Ibid, p. 19).

⁴⁶ <http://www.Kyiv.ukrstat.gov.ua/p.php3?c=512&lang=1>

Therefore, we can distinguish between the following groups of internal migrants in Kyiv:

Labour migrants

- Residential migrants from Kyiv region;
- Residential migrant from other regions;
- Pendulum migrants from Kyiv region;
- Pendulum migrants from other regions residing in the region;
- Circular migrants from Kyiv region;
- Circular migrants from other regions.

Educational migrants

- Educational migrants from Kyiv region;
- Educational migrants from other regions (including temporarily occupied Crimea and parts of Donbas).

Forced migrants

- Internally displaced people from Donbas and Crimea.

The pendulum migration contributes to the formation of migration intentions and many involved people consider it as a stage in further migration resettlement (Pozniak, 2007, p. 125).

Risks and challenges

The disproportions of socio-economic development of the regions of Ukraine significantly affect migration flows within the country. The migratory increase of the urban population causes expansion of man-made pollution causes deterioration of transport infrastructure and housing and communal problems. In the cities and suburban areas residential construction is chaotic and violates technical requirements, while social infrastructure remains undeveloped. The rapid expansion of urban agglomerations also requires modernization of infrastructure for processing or disposal of solid industrial and household waste (Ukrainske suspilstvo, 2018, p. 18).

Migrations to conurbations are accelerating depopulation of certain areas, especially with a high concentration of small towns and villages (Ibid., p. 20). In a first place negative consequences of internal migration will affect settlements with low resources, poor financial capacities and social infrastructure.

2.7 Political context

Ukraine gained independence in 1991. Contemporary Ukraine is a republic with the semi-presidential system of government known as 'premier-presidential model' when a parliamentary coalition appoints and dismisses the head of the cabinet and its ministers, while the president has power to dissolve the parliament and veto that enable him to take an active part in the legislative process. The President is regarded in the Constitution as a head of State and Prime-Minister a head of executive power. The president submits to the Parliament (Verkhovna Rada) the candidates for the positions of minister of defence and minister of foreign affairs, heads of the Prosecutor General's Office and the Security Service. If they don't pass the Parliament vote, the president can appoint them acting officials by the presidential decree. In general, the political field in Ukraine is quite competitive and the system of check and balances works if not perfectly but effectively enough to prevent shift to authoritarianism.

Since 1991 for the most time Ukrainian geopolitical strategy was basically multi-vector and oriented towards Russian Federation and CIS from the one hand and EU and Euro-Atlantic block on the other. It has been changed dramatically after revolutionary events in 2014 known as “Euromaidan” when Ukraine adopted a political course aimed at EU and NATO membership.

Some visible cleavages in Ukraine emerged since 1991 or were inherited from the Soviet period: linguistic, ethnic, political and ideational. Ukrainian studies scholars argue that none of them is significant enough to produce social and political conformation by themselves: “whilst clearly being diverse, Ukraine is not deeply divided along ethnic or even linguistic lines. Ethnicity, language, and political orientations correlate but do not necessarily match and reinforce each other.” (Podolian, Romanova, 2018).

“Democracy Index 2019” by the Economist Intelligence Unit (EIU) marks Ukraine “hybrid regime” (5.9/10 overall score) and ranked 78 out of 167 countries (Democracy Index, 2019). The other indicators include (score out of 10):

- Electoral process and pluralism - 7.42
- Functioning of government – 2.71
- Political participation – 6.67
- Political culture – 6.25
- Civil liberties – 6.47

“Freedom in the World index 2020” composed by the Freedom House (FH) regard Ukraine ‘partly free’.⁴⁷ It scores 62 points out of 100 (political rights 27/40, civil liberties 35/60). FU “Nations in transit index 2020” focused on democracy performance and transformations characterize the political system in Ukraine as a ‘transitional or hybrid regime’. It scores 40 points out of 100 (democracy percentage 39.88/100, democracy score 3.39/7) (Nations, 2020).

Mass violations of human rights were unknown in Ukraine until the annexation of Crimea and war in Donbas. Although cleavages are not strong enough to act as direct drivers of social-political conflicts in Ukraine, they could be used for political mobilisation orchestrated from outside, that happened when Russia used post-Euromaidan vacuum of power for annexation of Crimea and military intervention in Donbas both directly and through local proxies.

That led to the mass population exodus of IDPs from the affected regions. Most of them are located in Donetsk region – 0.5 million, Luhansk region – 300 thousand and Kyiv and Kyiv region – 200 thousand together). Numerous groups of IDP are also in Kharkiv, Dnipropetrovsk, Zaporozhye regions (Mihratsiia, 2019, p. 6).

Figure 10. Number of IDPs in 2014 – 2019 (1.000)

⁴⁷ <https://freedomhouse.org/country/ukraine/freedom-world/2020>

Employment of IDPs is growing slowly in recent years, and reached 46% as of June 2019. It is, however, still nine percentage points less than for the overall population of Ukraine (Ibid.).

The share of IDPs who do not intend to return to their previous places of residence even after the end of the conflict is 34% as of June 2019. At the same time only a small number of IDPs intend to go abroad: only 1% of respondents said they found a job abroad and 5% expressed interest in working abroad. This is primarily due to demographics composition of this category of the population - a high share elderly people, families with children (Ibid., p. 7) and a high level of paternalistic attitudes in their regions of origin, i.e. the predominance of orientations towards the state support, NGO and international organisations assistance.

2.8 Migration policies on internal/international mobility

Ukraine has a fairly detailed legal framework that regulates migration processes, and appropriate administrative institutions dealing with migrations were established. However, the main focus is on international migration, while internal migrations are mentioned only occasionally in these documents.

The work on the draft law on the "Concept of state migration policy" has been underway since 1999, and the Ukrainian Parliament (Verkhovna Rada) has tried to adopt it five times, most recently in 2010. These legislative proposals were initiated by the deputies and the Cabinet of Ministers. According to O. Malynovska, progress in addressing the question of strategic directions of migration policy was hindered, among other things, by the then confrontation of branches of power, mutual blocking by the parliament, the President and the Cabinet of Ministers any initiatives, not only in the field of migration (Malynovska, 2014).

The State Migration Service of Ukraine was established in 2010 as a central executive agency responsible for the implementation of national policy in the sphere of migration, combating illegal migration, citizenship, registration of individuals, refugees and other related issues.

It was not until 2011 that this concept was approved by a decree of the then President of Ukraine, Yanukovich. According to Ihor Markow, this concept was "abstract-declarative document, lacking internal content" and all the aspects and hints of migration problems enlighten by the Concept "stuck" at the level of abstract phrases without any delineation of the prospects for a real solution" (Markov, 2011).

The issue was put again on the political agenda in 2015, when the Ukrainian parliament adopted the "Law on External Labour Migration".⁴⁸ According to the Law, employment of a migrant worker in the host country can be carried out: by the Ukrainian executive bodies in accordance with the international agreements; by a commercial entity that provides employment mediation services abroad; by migrant workers independently. In the first and second case, before leaving for the host country, the migrant should be provided with a draft employment contract certified by a foreign employer (Ibid.).

This was followed by the 2017 "Strategy of State Migration Policy until 2025".⁴⁹ The Strategy underlines several objectives of the international migration policy (Ibid.):

- developing opportunities for temporary legal employment abroad as an alternative to permanent emigration;
- promoting educational exchange programs; raising public awareness of migration opportunities, including return;
- ensuring a permanent dialogue with the EU member states and other states on the protection of the rights of migrant workers, continuing the process of concluding international agreements on social protection and pensions with major migrant-receiving countries,
- updating bilateral international agreements on labour migration and intensifying cooperation with migrant-receiving countries.

⁴⁸ <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/761-19>

⁴⁹ <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/482-2017-%D1%80#Text>

The Strategy declares necessity of introduction of “a state credit system for returning migrants who want to start their own business, tax benefits for those who invest their earnings abroad in their own business, as well as measures to support the adaptation of re-emigrant children to the Ukrainian education system, including distance learning based on Ukrainian curricula, in particular, the study of the Ukrainian language abroad, upon return - additional training programs aimed at facilitating study in Ukraine, providing access to external independent knowledge assessment” (Ibid.).

Ukraine is a party of the European Convention on the Legal Status of Migrant Workers. It has agreements on the portability of old-age pensions with several EU member countries: Hungary, Romania, Latvia, Spain, Lithuania, Estonia, Slovakia, the Czech Republic, Bulgaria, Portugal and Poland. Country's government agencies also have bilateral memoranda of understanding (MOU) with government agencies responsible for migration in Lithuania, Portugal and the Czech Republic, while bilateral negotiations with the other EU member states are underway.

Internal migration is partially addressed in the “Strategy of demographic development until 2015” and “State strategy of regional development until 2020” adopted by the Cabinet of Ministry of Ukraine in 2006 and 2015 respectively.

The demographic development strategy admits the necessity of labour mobility management for the purpose of ensuring balanced socio-economic development of regions through stimulating the development of entrepreneurship, creation of new jobs in depressed regions, especially in science-intensive sectors, in the tourist industry, and transport infrastructure development in suburban areas of large cities. These measures were considered as means to prevent illegal migration abroad.

According to the regional development strategy, internal migration could help to overcome regional disproportions. The management of the interregional and intraregional labour mobility, in the first place pendulum migration, could help solving employment problems in redundant regions.

In a recent report on migration aspects of societal development in Ukraine internal labour force mobility is regarded as an alternative to the mass outmigration.⁵⁰ It was outlined in the “Strategy of State Migration Policy until 2025”:

“Internal migration in Ukraine, which could be an alternative to external migration, is carried out outside the plans and programs of regional development. It is focused on the most promising in terms of living and working conditions regions, especially the capital, engaging the most active representatives from rural and depressed regions, that narrows the prospects for their development, exacerbates regional disparities.”⁵¹

Development of the labour force mobility in Ukraine could be achieved through withdrawing of administrative barriers to freedom of movement, that means improving instruments of population accounting, of registration of residence and of issuance of documents, elimination of existing factors that lead to the reluctance of the landlords to register the place of residence, reducing the dependence of medical, administrative and other services on the registered place of residence (Ibid.).

⁵⁰ http://www.nas.gov.ua/text/pdfNews/migration_national_report_main_results.pdf P.31

⁵¹ <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/482-2017-%D1%80#Text>

Picture: Asya Tes/Unsplash.com

3. Results

This part of the report is based on the findings of the qualitative research conducted in 2021 in Kyiv – the capital city which for years has been the top place in Ukraine in regard to receiving internal migrants. The fieldwork for the project began with an expert focus-group on migration organised by Centre for Applied Anthropology in Kyiv in January 2021 in which six Ukrainian experts on various aspects of migration took part, sharing their knowledge and reflections on internal and international migration of Ukrainians. Due to the pandemic situation, the focus group took place online via Zoom. During the focus group several topics were mentioned, including: historical perspective on the drivers of migration, interconnections between internal and international migrations among various groups of migrants, present situation of the country and recent developments in relation to internal and international migration trends, future migration scenarios in the post-Covid period.

3.1 In-depth interviews

Following the desk research and the focus group, the sample frame for the project was created with the aim to reflect the heterogeneous structure of the internal migrant population. During the fieldwork 30 in-depth interviews were conducted according to a common interview scenario. The thematic focus of the research included research questions such as: How local factors drive migration propensities?, What factors attract migrants to the capital city? How do the character of migration drivers change? How does living in the “destination” city influence decisions to stay in the country or to migrate abroad? What other factors are at play in the migration decision-making? What is the role of social networks in internal and international migration processes? What are the migration scenarios in regard to international migration?

Among the individual interviews with migrants, 13 interviews were with men and 17 with women. The age of interviewees was between 20 to 62 years. Among them, there were 6 people aged 20 to 25, and 6 people older than 45. The largest age group in the sample (18 people) are people aged 26 to 45 years. They are the most economically active category of people and the most mobile, that is why it was crucial to include their experience of migration in the study. The sample included respondents of different education levels and specialisation as well as of various work experience.

The city selected as the main locus for this project was Kyiv which is both administrative and business centre of Ukraine. The offices of all large enterprises are located there. The field of IT technologies is one of the fastest-growing industries in the capital. In addition, the service sector is highly developed in the Kyiv region and numerous educational institutions are concentrated in the city offering a wide variety of options. At the same time, such sectors of the economy as heavy industry and the agricultural sector are not widely represented in the city. Thus, the structure of the research sample reflects the situation on the Kyiv labour market. Among the low-skilled workers, we were able to interview people of different professions, primarily in the field of services: a baker, craftsman, repair person, salesman, manicurist. The largest professional group interviewed were the middle-level workers. In the case of Kyiv, this is justified, as people in this category constitute a large segment of Kyiv's economy. Among the people interviewed were people of the following professions: teachers at schools and kindergartens, IT workers, accountants, photographers, recruiters, salespeople etc. Among the highly qualified employees, we interviewed NGO representatives, researchers, top managers, businessmen, and civil servants. Thus, our sample allowed us to cover the most economically active population of Kyiv and to represent people of various spheres and professions as widely as possible.

Our sample included people who moved from different regions of Ukraine, both remote and those bordering the Kyiv region. The study also presents people who have moved from agricultural regions, small towns, and large regional centres (such as Odesa, Vinnytsia, or Uzhhorod, Chernivtsy). In addition, the division of people into three groups, according to how many years they are in Kyiv (newcomers – people who arrived at Kyiv less than 5 years before 2021; longer stayers – 6-10 years before, and settled migrants – those who had been living in the capital for more than 11 years), gave us an opportunity to explore various reasons for migration: economic, political, socio-cultural and related to security. The sample included 8 persons who moved after 2014 from the temporarily occupied territories of Ukraine during the Russian-Ukrainian war in the East and in Crimea (4 persons who moved from the Crimea, 3 persons who moved from the Donetsk region, and one person who moved from Luhansk).

The majority of interviewees identified themselves as ethnic Ukrainians or noted Ukrainian citizenship as the main aspect in their identity. As far as the religious diversity is concerned, most interviewees were Orthodox Christians which reflects the religious landscape in the country. Some people considered themselves atheists (mostly young people aged 25-38). Also, the sample included Muslims (2 persons), a Catholic (1 person) and a Protestant (1 person).

3.2 Reasons for leaving

'In my native the city, there were not so many opportunities' - economic reasons

The dominance of economic factors in recent internal and international migration has been confirmed in our research. Since the early 1990s till now the decline of the economy has had a direct effect on migration processes. As O. Malinowska stressed: 'we live in a state of permanent crisis, the socio-economic reasons are decisive' (UAMigFG). Economic difficulties were presented as the most prevalent reason for leaving places of origin or previous settlement among our three categories of migrants: settled, long-term and newcomers. What's important, economic drivers are crucial not only in the case of rural areas, but also in cities. The majority of the respondents admitted that the need to find a job and to earn money was among the main drivers of internal migration from various regions of Ukraine. For instance, a 23-year old migrant woman came to the capital from a city in the Kyiv region: 'I came to Kyiv at the age of nineteen after graduating from a pedagogical college, because there are not enough jobs in my city' (MigUANF19). She was then followed by her sister who is now studying philology at a university in Kyiv. Another migrant who came to Kyiv seven years ago at the age of 28, underlined the centre – periphery nexus:

*The periphery is the periphery. That is, there is almost a fight for the slightest work.
(MigUALF15)*

The continuous socio-economic inequalities between regions are a major driver of internal migration. As many provinces offer much less opportunities in terms of jobs or salary than others, people move in search of better life standards.

Another example is the situation in Kherson, a regional centre and a port city in the south of Ukraine, which was described by a respondent who came to Kyiv seven years ago:

R: Is it difficult to find a job there in Kherson?

I: Yes.

R: And why?

I: Well, few suggestions are real. Large enterprises were closed. There was a combine plant, a shipyard. They are standing and there are no vacancies. There's just a small business offering. These enterprises are private. (...)

Positions, vacancies are few.

1990(MigUAML08)

An important factor which makes the situation at the labour market even worse is corruption, or the need to belong to some influential social or family networks. When job opportunities are scarce, those ties often influence the decision who would get a particular work. These problems can be seen in the context of “informality” of the Ukrainian social and economic system, i.e., weak institutions and tough economic conditions. Decision to migrate is thus embedded in macrostructures and the lack of perspectives for improvement.⁵²

A young professional from the Potlava region recalls his mother’s experience with work in their home village in the following words:

In 2010, she worked in a kindergarten, and when she left it, you can no longer find another kindergarten. You will be hired, if you are the godfather of the director there, and if you had a row with someone there, then the door will be closed for you. There is really lack of work.

(UAMigSM03)

For a 35 women who came to the capital from a town in the Kyiv region the reason for migration was similar:

I came to Kyiv in 2013. One of the problems I faced in my town was the lack of jobs. I could have a position there, I don't know there, even for the position of a cleaner - this is a problem, it is necessary to have some corruption ties, or to settle down and understand that you will work for a meagre salary and, roughly speaking, you will not be treated as to a full-fledged person.

(MigUALF15)

In migrants’ narratives three periods of modern Ukrainian history stand out as in terms of hardships and economic difficulties: the devastating 1990s, the 2008 global crisis, and then current time since the developments in 2014 – the Majdan protests, the occupation of Crimea and the beginning of war in eastern Ukraine.

Older migrants used to talk about their personal experiences during the first years after the fall down of the communist system. The transition era was marked by rapid deterioration of life standards. It was often contrasted with the economy of the Soviet Union which provided more jobs for people:

Well, that (earning a living) was not a problem in the Soviet Union. Then there were enough jobs.

(MigUAMLo8)

This was a village in the Kherson region on the border with the Mykolaiv region, where the estuary and were very beautiful places, but, unfortunately, there was actually no work. Back in the nineties, in the early nineties - there were the 1991-1992 years, when we just got there - there was still a cannery, there was a workshop for bottling mineral water, the greenhouse complex, and there were farms and large vineyards, fields, etc. which occupied such a leading position in the market. And then it all melted away and we all lost our jobs.

In the 1990s, the process of de-industrialization had a direct effect on the economic situation, as many factories which had employed local people all over Ukraine were closed down:

My parents (...) lived in Khmelnytsky region - as it is called, there was a sugar factory there. Now there are ruins. The sugar factory survived World War the second, unfortunately, did not survive Perestroika.

(UAMigSF02)

⁵² We thank T. Polek for pointing to this issue, which certainly needs further exploration.

Migration was then mostly a strategy of survival and satisfying basic needs. Even those who managed to keep their jobs did suffer huge difficulties and poverty, as the inflation was raging at that time and salaries were often insufficient to cover minimum daily expenses. Even basic food products were very costly compared to average earnings. In some cases, salaries were not paid at all for some periods of time:

It was the ninety-fourth year. We lived in a dormitory, and the dormitory stopped heating, and we had no alternative just to leave it. That time, salaries were not paid for years, and even the salary we received, it was too small. We can buy just a couple of loaves of bread for that money. But it was paid very, very rarely, they gave us flour and oil sometimes. It was horrible.

(UAMigSF01)

There were times when no one received anything, in the 1990s, for example, when teachers were not paid.

(MigUASF28)

Another interviewee from Chernivtsi recalled the mutual help of people who had to find ways to survive those hard times:

These were the 90s, it was not very good for everyone. I would not say that we were poor people, but there were moments when it was a little tough. (...) We weren't hungry. But there were moments when we bought products of poor quality (...). Saving methods were often used. Well, since my grandfather had great relatives who helped each other, there were 15 brothers and sisters in total. They often exchanged food, plus there were plots of land, which they also received all together, they were also nearby. (...) We used them as vegetable gardens, went there and planting some products. So what did I say we exchanged products. They helped each other.

(MigUALM26)

For some people, the prolonged situation of economic decline coupled with no prospects for better life led to decision to migrate, either internally or internationally, in many directions, often following migration path of their acquaintances, family members or neighbours:

Again, the evil nineties, when half the village went to Moscow, took everything out of the gardens because everything was taken for sale. That is, a lot was stolen and this was such empty work very often.

(MigUASF28)

In some narratives, the 2008 was mentioned as another economic crisis which affected the economic life in many households:

When there was a crisis in 2008, then of course there was less money and this directly affected the financial situation of my family, plus my mother once wanted to look for a job, but she could find, because in Kerch there are not so many job offers.

(UAMigLF05)

Economic situation in Ukraine deteriorated rapidly again after 2014 as a result of Russian invasion, war in the eastern territories and the annexation of Crimea. Moreover, in the post-Majdan period there was less hope for sustainable development and democracy, which led to a wave of "post-dream migrants" (Oleinikova 2017: 90).

As O. Pozniak argued those events have influenced migration patterns and led to an increase in emigration flows from Ukraine:

And when, after the events of 2014, the economic situation became worse, and earnings in Kyiv became less attractive, it served as a catalyst for increased external migration.

(UAMigFG)

Actually, in the case of Crimean Tatars the lack of jobs also had another dimension. Even before Russia took control over Crimea in 2014, job market for Tatars was restricted due to ethno-political issues:

At first I wanted to be a lawyer, but it was too difficult for Crimean Tatar to get a job in some civil service in a good position ... I can go to the police but for working in a public prosecution office I'll need some corruption ties - it was very, very difficult, because you had to pay a bribe, you had to have acquaintances in order to get a position like this.

(UAMigNF07)

Agricultural production

In our study, interviewees were not engaged in farming as a job. However, many people in rural areas had in their families some, smaller or bigger, plots of lands or vegetable gardens. Agricultural products were usually used for families' needs:

R: Did your family possess any agricultural plot, any piece of land?

I. Yes, it was at that time, we used it. (...)

R. And what was that?

I. I don't know its size, it's hard for me to say now. It was a fairly small area at the time. It was the preparation of food: potatoes, all kinds of preservation for the winter season.

(MigUALM21)

In some periods, however, it constituted an additional or even a substantial source of income:

Well, look, the economic situation .. In principle, I would not say that it was good, it's just these 1990-2000s - it has changed a little for the better, but still the level of income in our family compared to the whole village, yes, if we take the general village - it was middle. It was not the smallest, but it was far from what we wanted. Middle. Where did the income come from? Well, firstly, my parents worked at some jobs, and secondly, agriculture: cow, milk, well. (...)

We used to keep a lot of cattle. We had five cows. And in the last years of Kuchma's presidency, a lot of milk was delivered. Then hand over milk for UAH 1,700, this is when the father's salary was UAH 500, and here the milk brought UAH 1,700. But it was difficult.

(UAMigSM03)

A 39-year old interviewee who came to Kyiv from a village in the Cherkasy region told about her experiences:

We were somehow given a garden in the field (...). Once there was a collective farm in the village and there were cattle, and apparently, there were fields for grazing. And then, when the collective farm was closed and the cattle ran out, these fields were divided into gardens. It was very far to go there and these were the lands that were flooded, they were by the river, well, that is ... And they gave it to us. We used to plant vegetables there. But we always used it for ourselves, that is, never for sale. It was just for my family and it was very helpful. But even at that time, there were cattle. This, again, helped, because there was a bird, there were rabbits and piglets. When the parents built a house and moved, the neighbours gave them a calf, and it became a cow, so there was also milk. Now, for many years now, my parents have only had chickens.

(MigUASF28)

Although cultivating vegetables, fruit, or raising animals is quite common, in particular in rural regions, they do not provide enough economic support for families. High costs related to agriculture often discourage people from cultivating food or keeping farm animals. In Crimea, where the political situation is very tense, water is exceptionally expensive and many families give up this field of activity. Such was the case of a young woman from Kerch:

Just for our needs, we never kept animals. And in fact, now it is very difficult to grow something - very expensive water. Therefore, once they grew potatoes, tomatoes, there are some trees, apples - something like that, but in fact in Crimea it is very difficult to grow something, very expensive.

(UAMigLF05)

In many cases, animals are kept for families' needs. They can be sold, but it is not considered as a regular income.

The opinions on the attractiveness of work in the agricultural sector differed among the interviewees. Many Ukrainians consider it nowadays to be unprofitable and difficult. They underline low market prices for agricultural products contrasted with high costs of energy and infrastructure. What's important – the perceived unprofitability of agriculture is not linked directly to environmental factors, as it is common in many vulnerable countries which experience droughts and scarcity of water. On the other hand, there are prospects for farmers who are able to acquire large areas of land and consider farming as a professional job. As a man from a rural area in the Poltava region narrated:

One or two people are working as farmers in our village with 500 population of 500. It all starts with an old Soviet tractor, little by little, some fields are sown, and in ten years you will probably buy yourself a new tractor. But not immediately.

(UAMigSM03)

Modern agriculture is considered as an option for work for young people, but it is known that it requires financial capital, knowledge, a lot of hard work and patience.

Limited educational opportunities

Another common reason driving migration to the capital and other large cities is education. For the younger generation, in particular, educational motives for migration are clearly visible. Young people often choose bigger urban centres as a place to enter higher educational institutions. In some places, state-funded educational institutions are being closed and young people have to search for other options. Moreover, the competition in such cases increases and there is more pressure to leave for education to a bigger city.

For a young woman who left Crimea in 2013, the lack of attractive educational opportunities locally made her move to Kyiv:

There are not so many educational institutions in Crimea, in Simferopol, in Sevastopol there are educational institutions. In Kerch, the Vernadsky branch was closed – so, well, I had a choice to enter, for example, to Simferopol, but I deliberately did not do this, because I understood that it was not a very good choice. Low level of education, let's say. Plus, I know that students, for example, from Kerch (the distance between Kerch and Simferopol 250 kilometres) did not even give a hostel, they could say – 'You can go home every day from Kerch to Simferopol.'

(UAMigLF05)

A 23-year old woman from the city of Mironovka in the Kyiv region pointed to the problem of closing of colleges:

R: And in Mironovka you had a secondary special, right, in college?

I: In Mironovka we have no colleges, they closed it down. There are only schools. I graduated from college in a neighbouring town, the city of Boguslav. (...) The number of state budget places is limited. And they are restricting, closing down colleges. And lyceums are made from schools. And more serious selection. And who can enter this lyceum - these must be the smartest, most reasonable children. And only after graduating from this lyceum, people will be able to enter the university. And it comes down to the fact that there will be no educational institution

such as a college. This, of course, is very sad, because what to do for those who could not enter for one reason or another? Or whose parents cannot pay for education.

(MigUANF19)

In some interviews, the problem of corruption in the educational sector was mentioned. It obviously impacts the quality of education. A former student of biology at the Uzhhorod National University evaluated her experiences as follows:

I: Well, in terms of the level of education, it is more on the shoulders of students than on teachers, but it is special subjects that are taught at a good level. And if we talk about others that are not applied in practice, such as the economy and so on, then corruption simply goes beyond scale, you have to pay.

R: That is, there was such a corruption component, right?

I: Yes, that is, you have to know the subject and pay. If you don't pay the maximum mark for you is 3.

(MigUANF24)

Corruption was raised as a topic while assessing the quality of education, but for respondents it was not a direct driver for migration. Rather, migration for educational reasons was associated with more opportunities, wider choice of specialisations and a better level of education.

At the expert Focus Group, the topic of education was raised several times. Tina Polek discussed the process of educational migration from villages to cities. This direction of migration continues and, in her opinion, young people usually move to cities to enrol at a school or university. Work comes as a second main reason for this cohort. She has noticed a new trend in youth's preferences after 2015 – migration from rural areas directly to foreign universities:

When I was writing my research (2015), it was normal to go to Kyiv or another city centre for study. Recently, going abroad to study has become the norm not only for urban residents, but also for rural residents. Such a reorientation has taken place, and there is an opportunity to migrate not only within the country, but also abroad - this is such a new phenomenon. Life in the village is not getting better, but now there is another option

(UAMigFG).

Cities are thus no longer a typical step in migration. Young people from villages use new opportunities and go abroad directly from their places of residence.

Little opportunities for career development

Research has also revealed some important socio-cultural factors which influence the decision to migrate. In many regions, there is a limited choice of jobs. For young people, who aspire to work in sectors which are not available in their localities, this is the reason to migrate – at first, to bigger cities. Those internal migrants do not find attractive options for life and career in their villages or cities. A migrant who came to Kyiv from Kerch told about the scarcity of options which were available to young people in his place of origin:

In Kerch, my native the city, there were not so many opportunities to be realised, it is very kind of understandable. Mostly people in our city, well, they are either engaged in private entrepreneurship, or men go to the sea ...(...). They studied to be mechanics or navigators and go on voyages. Well, these are the two main types of earnings. As if I was not going to do either one or the other, that's why I'm here.

(UAMigLF05)

For a university graduate, physical work which was available in his home village was not attractive:

R: And were there some kind of private businesses with some jobs - was there enough?

I: There were enough of them in the father's sphere, look, this is a village, this is an agribusiness type, this is

Poltava region, that is. And getting a driver is not a problem, the problem is that it's a little hard to work and in a certain period he threw his back out, so he had some problems with the health. He worked on Tavria, a car - a brand that is absolutely lousy what can be the type. He caught a cold on it, for example, that's the problem, yes.
(UAMigSM03)

It is, therefore, not just simple lack of jobs, but lack of jobs many young people aspire to:

There are just blue-collar jobs in the village. Well, it's not a profession, it's the ability to manage around the house. But this is the basis. But in the village to get a profession, in fact, is impossible. Impossible. We have it concentrated in the city.
(MigUANM12)

Apart from the fact that large urban centres offer much more possibilities of employment, they also offer more options for training, internships, various activities for personal development, non-formal education or career development.

Attractiveness of urban culture and lifestyle

Another socio-cultural driver of internal migration is related to lifestyle – the willingness to live in an attractive place. For some of our interviewees it was important to choose a city with active cultural life and recreational facilities. Urban life is often contrasted with a village in terms of general atmosphere, lifestyle and opportunities. 33 year-old interviewee who came to Kyiv two years ago explained her choice:

R. Was this decision (to go to Kyiv) easy? How long did you hesitate?
I. Yes, easy, because by that time I was already getting bored in Vinnytsia. It's like a very quiet, family town. You already know every street there. Each institution has already visited, each institution 10 times. That is, it is as if ... I'm a little stagnant there. And I wanted somewhere further. And after Scotland, when I came, it was also such a very contrast, I wanted something new, somewhere to develop something to do. Well, Kyiv was a very good alternative. I immediately ... almost immediately agreed to something new.
(MigUANF13)

The perception of attractiveness is also changeable and complex. For example, for a migrant from Odessa who chose Kyiv 13 years ago, his city is no longer attractive, especially in comparison with the capital. In contrast, for people coming directly from villages Odessa presents some advantages:

Odessa is quite conservative. And from the point of view of development opportunities, they are limited there, this is unambiguous. I am now observing a rather interesting situation in Odessa, which did not exist before. This city provides opportunities for the newcomers from the region, let's call it rural areas of the Odessa region. The number of rural inhabitants from Odes'ka oblast who come to Odessa grows. They find in Odessa, which is a big city, for sure better possibilities than in the villages. These people have more ways to find themselves in a big city.
(UAMigSM18)

Political reasons 2014 - 2021

Regarding other drivers of internal migration, O. Pozniak stated during the Focus Group that migration drivers are always complex, but under some circumstances some of them become dominant:

In such cases, when migration is voluntary, when it does not cause any serious threats to life, health, and so on, the economic factors are fundamental. After 2014, if we talk about IDPs, then the economic factor will not play such a significant role, here security, ethnic and religious factors play a bigger role. But after the transition to a safe area economic factors play a significant role for further migration.
(UAMigFG)

Political drivers of internal and international migrations in Ukraine are relatively new compared to other drivers in the country's recent history. Certainly, the year 2014 was a crucial breakthrough in the history of contemporary migration in Ukraine and new waves of migrations took place, including forced migration. The unlawful 'referendum' and the annexation of Crimea by the Russian Federation completely changed the situation in the peninsula. According to E. Adzhieva, there are no reliable statistics on the number of migrants who left the region due after 2014 which constitutes a challenge for those who help them. It is confirmed, however, that some people left Crimea out of fear of persecution or violation of human rights, and some due to the disagreement with pro-Russian authorities and their policies. For example, for some Crimean Tatars, the decision to migrate was linked with the unwillingness to collaborate with the occupation administration (UAMigFG, Adzhieva E.). For many people who continue to live in Crimea, life has become more difficult in many aspects. Travelling between the region and the mainland Ukraine is very restricted, and controls at the borders discourage people from regular mobilities.

Military actions in Donbas area also led to significant waves of internal migration. Actually, the Internally Displaced People (IDPs) are the most researched group in terms of their migrant status and plans. Among our interviewees there were people who came to Kyiv after 2014 from Crimea (four people), Donetsk region (3 people) and from Luhansk (1 person). Some of them arrived at the capital immediately after the war began due to the lack of security, e.g., :

I arrived in Kyiv 6 years ago, it was November 2014, now I remember. I remember exactly when I was 30 years old. Probably 2014, autumn 2014. It was so long ago, the memory erases all these moments. Why did I come? Because heavy shelling started. You know such, very hard shelling. When somewhere 100-200 metres from me a rocket exploded, hit a car, and a whole family died there.
(MigUALF20)

The discourses of our respondents from those areas reveal the importance of political factor in the most recent migration waves:

In fact, a lot of people leave Crimea. Well, young people are leaving, of course, all the time, it's a constant process. But many people and the older generation left Crimea because of the occupation, even people who are 60 years old, 70, there are such cases.
(UAMigLF05)

The situation and status of the IDPs are complex. They can't be easily regarded as migrants because, as Ruslan Khalikovych Khalikov argued, many of them still reside in the same place and did not leave their regions. Only from time to time they travel to the areas controlled by Ukraine. What's important as well, this group does not want to be labelled as migrants. Even those who moved internally want to be treated as part of the local community, not as strangers. This is reinforced by local politics which grant them rights to vote and support integration tools.

One of our interviewees told us about her husband who faced direct threats because he was a member of the Mejlis of the Crimean Tatars and worked in the civil society area. Even though he intended to stay to fight for his land and people, the situation became too tense and people involved in the political opposition were arrested, so he was forced to escape. His family joined him later in Kyiv. Apart from the family reunification, politics also played a role in the interviewee's case:

R. You didn't go because of political reasons?
I. Well, yes, this is because of politics, it is of principle, because I, like my spouse, carry out human rights activities, speak publicly at very many international venues, and it is unambiguously unsafe for us to go to Crimea.
(MigUALF11)

I arrived in Kyiv 6 years ago, it was November 2014, now I remember. I remember exactly when I was 30 years old. Probably 2014, autumn 2014. It was so long ago, the memory erases all these moments. Why did I come? Because heavy shelling started. You know such, very hard shelling. When somewhere 100-200 metres from me a rocket exploded, hit a car, and a whole family died there.

(MigUALF20)

Political situation has a direct impact on the economy and security. A Crimean Tatar who took part in our research said that she has decided to move to Kyiv two years ago because of those intertwined factors:

This is because the situation is unpleasant, it is impossible to work, there are constant threats, and there is no sense of security.

(UAMigNFo7)

Many companies decided to leave the Crimea after 2014, so even for non-Tatar population job opportunities shrank and made people leave their residence places. A Russian IT specialist migrated from Sevastopol to Kyiv in 2016 because he lost his job. According to him, in his field only the businesses connected to Russia could thrive further:

In the field of IT, for example, after 2014 it became not very good. By the way, this is one of the reasons, for which I moved to Kyiv, in fact, because after the imposition of sanctions and other things in relation to Russia in 2015, it became clear that choice of work becomes less and less. Because all foreign customers, for whom it was possible to work, they simply stopped working with Crimea. And many of the acquaintances who worked in IT at that time were forced, even if they did not want it, were forced to move. Someone to St. Petersburg, someone to Bulgaria, someone to Europe. Some guys went to Thailand for a couple of years. Simply, because with Crimea, many firms after all this story and sanctions, they just stop working. It turns out that from the whole world there is only Russia with which you can work, if it is about IT in Crimea.

(UAMigNM06)

3.3 Reasons for choosing a destination

As it was mentioned in the previous part of the report, Kyiv city ranks top in Ukraine in terms of development indexes. It is, therefore, not surprising that the capital is the main recipient of migrants from all over the country. As the International Organisation for Migration states in its report: 'In the 2000's, the population of the capital grew by 20,000 people per year due to an influx from other regions' (Migration in Ukraine, 2016). When we asked in our research about the main reasons for choosing Kyiv as a place of destination, we got several answers. The most common answer was related to the economic situation: the wide availability of jobs, higher salary and many more choices for work for highly-skilled professionals in the capital than in other regions. Before recent deterioration of economic situation in Ukraine, Kyiv was an attractive place to live and work for many groups of workers:

On the one hand, more educated people, especially at a time when Ukraine was developing more successfully, had the opportunity to realise themselves in the national economy, and have a fairly high salary, and ensure a high standard of living by migration inside Ukraine, for example, to Kyiv.

(Olena Anatoliivna Malinovska, UAMigFG)

There is only one problem - everything is low-paid. Well, that is, even if you are an employee the income level is still lower if you live in a village. Salaries are two or three times lower than in Kyiv.

(UAMigSM03)

Differences of development levels are related not only to strictly economic aspects, such as jobs and the level of salary, but also to other aspects of everyday life. A bakery worker who came to Kyiv from Kherson region gave an example of electricity problems in her native settlement:

There, perhaps, were no such problems with electricity here in Kyiv, because in Kherson region, there were two hours of light, two were not, and so this is the economy. It's just that somehow you don't notice it in summer, it's just a catastrophe in winter. And sometimes there was no light for three hours, they turned it on for an hour. You just don't have time to do anything and it's nothing. And then we came here, looked around and saw that there was, well, absolutely another life, another level of earnings and absolutely another life. Even so, we thought that

even if we rent an apartment, it will still be better, yes. And the time "X" for us had come.
(UAMigSF01)

Kyiv is perceived as a city of opportunities for those who aspire for self-development. This factor is especially important nowadays, whereas earlier the need for personal advancement was less significant compared to economic motives. Internal migration is also a way for social mobility and improving one's social status. As T. Polek has stressed, since the Soviet era, there was a perception that being a "Kyivite", i.e, the inhabitant of the capital city, is a privilege and opens paths to a better life.

A woman who graduated from a college with two specialisations – in seamstress and accounting – presented her views on the capital city:

Well, I see prospects in Kyiv. Even if you start from a small position, there is an opportunity for career growth. Even if you start from the position of a salesman, you are in principle, if you are active, positive and well-disposed to work, you can, in principle, grow up the career ladder and you don't need a long period of time. Five years is enough to get up two positions easily.
(MigUALF15)

After arriving at Kyiv she worked at first as a seller. But, as she was ambitious and interested in psychology, she managed to find work as a recruiter.

The wider set of options for career is a key factor for the youth who wants to develop themselves, change work for a bigger company, work in their specialities or learn new things:

Young people from rural areas go to Odessa to study, and in general, they stay there. They do not return to the villages and get a job somewhere. And this is a kind of working model, which, in principle, works today. The guys who strive for something more, of course, are very eager to move to Kyiv. Simply because the opportunities for self-development and creativity in Odessa are still limited.
(UAMigSM18)

Before moving, I was engaged in advertising and marketing, and was a creative copywriter in Chernivtsi in a small agency. Then I moved to Kyiv to the same position. Actually, this was one of the reasons why I moved, in connection [with the search] for a larger agency. At the moment, I'm an IT developer who has tied up with creativity. Game developer in an IT company.
(MigUALM26)

Then I went to a graphic design studio. All this time I was learning something new. Design is such a thing where you are constantly learning. And when I moved to Kyiv for this job in IT, I just started from scratch, too, I also learned a lot of new things. Well, this is self-study. I took more language courses, studied French for two years.
(MigUANF13)

This narrative of Kyiv as a place attracting ambitious people appeared in a couple of interviews. Respondents were speaking about courses and training they completed and of many opportunities to socialise with wide circles of people which was important for their career.

Apart from job-related reasons, it is clear that lots of young people come to Kyiv to study. In this regard, the capital is also the place where a lot of diverse educational opportunities are available. In respondents' opinions, the quality of education is also higher than in many other places, so it is attracting ambitious young people. Those reasons were reflected in many interviews:

Somewhere in the 10th grade I did not know exactly where I wanted to go. It seemed to me that it was difficult to enter Kyiv, especially Shevchenko, that you had to have very high scores because I wanted to be on a budget. And

after I entered the Ukrainian Academy of Leadership, I studied there for a year. My ambitions have increased a bit and I realised that I have nothing to lose. I passed the external examination very well, and I understood, looked at the ratings last year that I could move to Kyiv, enter Shevchenko University. That's what came up. The first such main reason is education. I wanted to study either at the Kyiv-Mohyla Academy or at Taras Shevchenko's, because I think it was the two best universities in our country at that time.

(MigUANF10)

Those who wanted a really good education, so specialised, they went to Kyiv, Lviv, abroad to Poland. Those who were not so ambitious remained.

(MigUANF13)

There are also socio-cultural aspects of migration decision-making. For young people, in particular, the field of leisure activities, events, and entertainment plays a role in their life and that is what makes Kyiv attractive as well. A 32-years old financial director from a village in Transcarpathia moved to Kyiv after having studied in Lvov. She presented her perspective in the life in the capital:

Well, it's more fun here. That is, many areas, entertainment, more activities (...). Well, development opportunities and prospects. That is, there are many more of them in the city.

(UAMigSF02)

She studied in Lviv because her parents encouraged her to choose that city and she liked it a lot. But then, after gaining a diploma, she moved to Kyiv as she wanted something more:

These were purely my ambitions. After all, the capital, a big city, is bigger than Lviv. And the parents were not against it.

(UAMigSF02)

Social networks, including family ties, play a crucial role in the choice of destination. They facilitate mobility and settlement processes. For many respondents, the presence of relatives or friends gave them necessary contextual knowledge and helped in navigating the city. They shared information about vacancies that could be interesting to potential migrants. Moreover, those networks were the source of a pragmatic aid in finding accommodation or a job:

My dad was alive at that time, he lived here in Kyiv. Here. He is such an ardent patriot of Ukraine. He lived most of his life in Ukraine, even though he is from Rostov (...). And he took me, took me to Kyiv. Helped me the first time, until I got to my feet. With his wife.

(MigUALF20)

Not all internal migrants had someone else to take care of them. Many arranged the whole process of resettlement on their own.

Another factor, which was not mentioned so far, is family reunification. It is also an important driver of migration, as the family members try to find a place to stay together. Among our interviewees there were also such cases when after one person got a job in the capital, soon the rest of family followed their movement, e.g.:

At first, my husband was relocated to Kyiv. I was alone with my daughter for a whole year. Husband came time after time, but still he was mostly in Kyiv, because it is expensive to drive more frequently. We first lived in Rivne. And then one day we decided it wasn't good to meet once a month - the family should be together.

(UAMigLF04)

It is also important to note the preferences for internal migration over international. O. Malinovska underlined that for many migrants, especially those lacking capabilities to go abroad (lack of knowledge of foreign languages, lack of social connections in other countries, etc.), internal migration is considered to be a 'safer and less risky' choice (UAMigFG).

3.4 Future migration intentions

Our research indicates three major types of intentions among the persons that we have interviewed: to return to the places of origin, to migrate further within the country or abroad (a more popular option), and to stay in the city and the country. We have also detected in the research material some opinions that could be qualified as "being undecided" or "still searching" similar to the ones identified by Eade et al. during their research on Poles in the UK and classified as "searchers" or by the category of "intentional unpredictability" (2007). We consider this the fourth type of intention although a less prevalent one. In contrast to the research data from other case studies from outside of Europe – Senegal, Tunisia and Iraq - the narrative of irregular migration is almost entirely absent in Ukraine. This is mainly due to the possibilities of easy legal migration to Poland and other countries of the European Union. We start our analysis with the exploration of the least prevalent intention among our interviewees, that is to return to the place of the origin, and then move on to analyse much more frequently indicated motivations in the collected data, to migrate or to stay. At the end we briefly elaborate also on the "undecided" voices in the collected data.

"The goal should always be to return home ..." - Intentional Returnees

The intention to return was very strongly emphasised by all our interviewees who were forced to leave their places due to war and/or occupation of their territory by Russia. They migrated to Kyiv not because they wanted to, but because many of them could face persecution or even death if they had stayed in their villages, towns and cities. This situation in particular concerned those openly criticising the occupation as well as members of some religious minorities. As one of the experts interviewed in the course of the research pointed out:

On the territories under Russian control, there were just two options, either to be persecuted or to leave. And representatives of the Hizb ut-Tahrir, for example, or Jehovah's Witnesses, organisations that are banned in Russia, left the Crimea. Probably even bigger problems (with rights of religious minorities) were in Donbass. In the first years, there was a generally insane situation with religious freedoms: persecution, terror etc. Accordingly, in 2014, many religious organisations have contributed to the departure of their members. If we are talking about international organisations, they left these territories in an organised manner. Most of their properties in uncontrolled areas were then expropriated. In addition, many religious public figures supported the pro-Ukrainian line during the Maidan and after the Maidan in Donetsk there was a so-called religious marathon in which various religious organisations participated. As a result, all these activists had to leave Donetsk as soon as possible. The Jewish community in Donetsk actually split into two parts. A significant part of them left Donbas and the communities resumed their activities in Kyiv. The whole community moved to controlled territory. But it cannot be said that all believers have left. And they have no reason to return, there are rather reasons to migrate for those who had not yet left.

(UAMigSF03)

The case of Crimean Tatars who had to flee the Crimea as result of the Russian takeover is particularly dramatic because of the earlier history of forced migration, that is the expulsion of the entire community by Stalin in 1944 (Aydingun and Aydingun 2007). Some of our interviewees complained that those deported during the Second World War did not manage to return yet and a new wave of forced migration took place. This tragic history and even earlier expulsions after the Crimean War were recalled by the Crimean Tatar interviewee in the following way:

(...) After the deportation in 1944, about 100.000 Crimean Tatars did not have the opportunity to return to Crimea. Ukraine did not create favourable conditions for return. If there was some kind of financial support or a guarantee that you would be given a piece of land, or at least some apartment, or even a room in a dormitory, yes, then, perhaps, many would have moved. But people did not receive such guarantees, there were difficulties with obtaining citizenship in general. This procedure was very complicated. Then many did not stay. About 100000 Crimean Tatars remained far beyond the borders. I'm not even talking about those who were deported to Siberia and who somehow stayed there, put down roots, created families, again lacking financial opportunities to return. And, well, that is, now today there are no guarantees that even those Crimean Tatars, even if there is a de-occupation of Crimea, whether they will return or not. And this is a great pain for our people because there are so few of us. We are indigenous people and we are endangered. Russia has done everything to make us a minority on our land. After the annexation of 1783, our population was oppressed, and right now, the current situation after 2014, so everything is really complicated now.

(MigUALF11)

An important emotional and symbolic tie with Crimea was also expressed by other Crimean Tatar interviewees. The intention to return to the de-occupied peninsula was also linked with the perception of life in Kyiv as a temporary one and not a true "home". This sense of temporality of the current situation is clearly detectable in the following in the opinion of the following interviewee who said:

I do not perceive Kyiv as a home, I feel like a guest here. Ukraine is my native state, of course, for me it is connected with Kyiv. But I look at Kyiv through the eyes of an observer, through the eyes of a guest. Naturally, everything is so beautiful, it is impossible not to fall in love with it. If ever there is an opportunity to return to Crimea, of course I will. I can't even imagine now what will happen in the future. I cannot imagine myself as an elderly woman who has lived all her life in Kyiv. (UAMigNF07)

These deep connection with Crimea among the Crimean Tatars and the efforts to maintain it while being away was very pertinently captured by another female interviewee – forced migrant from the peninsula who pointed out:

Our grandparents, parents, and we weren't coming back to Crime after the deportation just to leave it and go in search of a better life. The Crimean Tatars have a genetic connection with our land, homeland, we truly love Crimea, we love it tremendously. Although, perhaps, there are better places in the world, beautiful places, that is, it is not a goal to go somewhere in search of some new life. I absolutely do not mind if young people go somewhere, get higher education, somewhere in the Sorbonne or somewhere in the USA, in one of the best universities of the higher league. But the goal should always be to return home and bring something useful, good for your homeland, for your people, so that in this only way you can be strong. And even if, despite the fact that you are forced to live outside your homeland under some circumstances, it is very important to preserve your identity, to convey this whole, this value to your children, so that they always know about it, and preserve their language, culture. Living here, my husband and I try to raise our children this way, to make them proud of being who they are, to make them know their roots, history, traditions, and their native language. Although it is very difficult.

(MigUALF11)

She has also probably most strongly expressed the desire to return to Crimea if only the circumstances allow it. She has argued that:

We all have a desire for Crimea to be de-occupied in the nearest future in order for all Crimean Tatars to return to their historical homeland. I cannot tell everyone, but I would like to live there, to be able to return home. Well, maybe it's good for someone to be here, in a big city with more opportunities, it's more possible to make money here. But in any case, any Crimean Tatar would like to be able to safely travel to Crimea, visit his relatives, and not be afraid to cross some borders.

(MigUALF11)

While speaking about the intentions of the wider community she has pointed out that:

I can't say for everyone, maybe a certain number of people will return. Some will want to return; others will not want to return. We cannot yet predict how everything will turn out. Well, this is already difficult, of course, when people leave, when people settle down somewhere, start from zero again, and again. It is difficult to change everything again. I don't know, of course, how other people would behave in such a situation. It's hard to say for someone how it will be. For my husband and me, there is no question anymore. In our family, this is unambiguous, if there is a de-occupation, we will definitely return to Crimea.

(MigUALF11)

Because of this very strong connection with the ancestral land some of the members of the Crimean Tatar community in spite of having the opportunities to migrate outside of Ukraine and obtain international protection in various countries of the world decided to stay in Ukraine. The key reason behind such a decision was to stay close to Crimea and if the circumstances allow return to the peninsula. This was intentions are for example expressed by one of our interviewees in the following way:

Well, I am fluent in English, for me, it can be said as a native language as well. For me there is no difference: I speak Russian, Ukrainian and English fluently. In general, nothing prevents me from taking everything and moving. Even in 2014 there were a number of countries to which we could go. My husband is a member of the Mejlis of the Crimean Tatar people – that is a representative body, which in 2016 was banned by the Supreme Court of Crimea and called "an extremist organisation". There was a different decision of the International Court of Justice, but, unfortunately, Russia does not comply with it and today is persecuting all members of the Mejlis. A number of countries were ready to grant political asylum, in any case, if we applied, it would be 100%. But we did not set a goal to run away, our goal is not to run somewhere, we set ourselves a goal to fight for our rights here. The Russian Federation breaks not only Ukrainian legislation, but they also break their own Constitution, they break international law. That is why we didn't even think of going anywhere in search of a different life. My husband and I were raised that way.

(MigUALF11)

At the same time the same interviewee pointed out that not all Crimean Tatars that left the peninsula after the Russian takeover have the same attitude as she and her husband and left Ukraine in search of better living conditions in Europe or elsewhere. She has said that:

There are so many people among our friends who first moved here, then, faced with a lot of difficulties, corruption in the country, without receiving any guarantees, and they have moved further in search for a better life. In this case, they've searched for a better life, better conditions, or some kind of guarantee. They moved to the USA, to Canada, to Turkey. There are some Crimean Tatars who moved to Poland. And by the way, the state of Ukraine does not even have these statistics, if we talk about statistics. And it is very important to us to know how many people left Crimea at all. It has been said that it is about fifty thousand. But how many of them are Crimean Tatars? Even state authorities here won't answer this question, because there is no statistical data. That is, when you register as a forced migrant, like an IDP, no one records whether you are a Crimean Tatar, because we all have citizenship of Ukraine. And so this statistic is not available. Approximately we are counting in our organisation. We know that about 20,000 Crimean Tatars have definitely left Crimea. Many of them settled compactly in various places of residence of mainland Ukraine. These large groups of Crimean Tatars are now in Kyiv, Lviv, Dnipro, there is a small number of Crimean Tatar families in Grebla, this is near Vinnitsa. There are several families in Vinnitsa itself. Then it is Odessa, with several families in Drohobych, its Volhynia. Many are in Genichesk, Khersonska oblast, some are in Kherson. Unfortunately, many are dispersed in different places. And there is generally no clear information about how many Crimean Tatars have left Ukraine.

(MigUALF11)

Our interviewees have also pointed out that even the temporary returns have been negatively impacted not only by “the political exacerbations” but also by the Covid-19 pandemic, which partially disrupted standard drivers of migration. One of the interlocutor has pointed out that:

I was last in Crimea in October 2019. For me, this is catastrophically long, but it is connected with the lockdown, with the quarantine, and being afraid of Covid-19. At first I was worried about my parents, now I am worried about my husband's parents that I could infect them. For example, if I come to Crimea, I will not sit at home, because I have a lot of relatives and a lot of friends there, plus my places in Crimea, which I used to visit, the forests, the mountains. That is why I can somehow bring this disease. For me, these are certain experiences, so I am waiting for when there is a suitable moment, they will be vaccinated and I can go.
(UAMigNF07)

Interested in Further Migration

A significant number of our interviewees in spite of the initial migration expressed the desire to migrate from Kyiv to other parts of Ukraine or more commonly abroad. As far as the first type of mobility is concerned our interviewees rarely spoke about their intention to migrate internally within Ukraine. If they did it is because they believe that their life outside of the capital city would be qualitatively better. The two interviewees who spoke about it wanted to move out of Kyiv either to Chernigov or Lviv. The first interviewee who wanted to move to Chernigov pointed out that:

In general, in the future, I would like to live somewhere near Kyiv. Maybe in 10-15 years, I would like to live in Chernigov. I really like this city. But this is on condition that I would have a job, for example, remote. I always think about, if I go to some city, what will I do there, what will I do there for a living. This is, let's say, the main factor. (...) I get tired of Kyiv, because it is still noisy. There is a very fast pace of life. Kyiv can still be quite dirty. There is significant air pollution. If, I don't know, in 10-15 years I would rather go there for a life in retirement. If I am still alive. It is a city where the pace of life is slower. That is, Chernigov is more comfortable, small. And this is probably the main reason why I would like to live there.
(UAMigLF05)

The second interviewee who was considering migrating internally spoke about it in the following way:

I would probably like to move to Lviv (...). It is closer to Europe. Well, just live in some other city. Well, quarantine ... My job allows, in principle, to work from any point of the globe. And if somewhere there is an opportunity to move, I, in principle, will most likely use it. Unless there is some other project here that will be more interesting. Lviv is the only city where I am considering moving. (...) because there, in principle, it is not far from the parents. You can come a little more often, there is just 4 hours to drive. My girlfriend's grandmother lives there, so it will be suitable to look after her, sometimes to visit. Just a change of scenery. Because there is no difference where to spend this quarantine time in Kyiv or Lviv. Well, plus it is closer to Europe from there. Then I considered moving to some other country. So far, in which one, it is necessary to figure it out. And it is very much tied to what kind of work it will be. Therefore, there is no specific country.
(MigUALM26)

Both interviewees were not ruling out at the same time the prospect of moving out the country but very strictly linked it with job opportunities.

The last motivation, namely the economic one, was one of the major drivers behind the intentions to migrate abroad. Among young persons in their twenties it was frequently linked with the plan to study abroad. As one of the experts during our focus group noticed “Recently, going abroad to study has become the norm not only for urban residents, but also for rural residents. Such a reorientation has taken place, and there is an opportunity to migrate not only within the country, but also abroad - this is such a new phenomenon. Life in the village is not getting better, but now there is another option”. (UAMigFG02) One of the countries which

host the largest number of Ukrainian students is Poland where their number has risen from 37,8 thousand in the academic year 2017-2018 to 39,2 thousand in the academic year 2018-2019 (Pędziwiatr et al. 2021: 87). One of the young interviewees trained as a manicure master, in the following way spoke about her intentions to migrate abroad:

Somehow I don't see any prospects here and want to migrate. Yes, I am not actively working on this yet. Because, you know, I have a lot of things that need to be closed (...) I should erect a monument on the mummy's tomb, I need to close some nuances there. Learn English. You need to earn something for the beginning. At least some amount of money. But still, I plan to leave for another country next year. (...) I have no relatives anywhere there. Therefore, I will have to relocate somehow independently, either to friends or to a place where I don't know anyone.
(MigUALF20)

As one may see, the fact that she neither masters English nor has a big social network puts her off from the plan to relocate abroad.

Another interviewee who seriously took into account his linguistic competences and the choice of the prospective destination countries was the following one who pointed out that:

I would be interested to live for some time in another country, just to compare. (...) Most of all I am impressed by the English-speaking countries: Great Britain, the USA, Canada. Because it would be the easiest thing to do. In general, my level of English is not bad. It would be pretty easy for me to adapt. (...) I don't have enough time and perseverance to take up the study of the foreign language, although I understand that on the spot when you are conventionally already there, it would be much easier. I like that.
(MigUALM21)

Yet another interviewee for whom going to an English speaking country was important argued that "I wanted to be in an English-speaking country, that is, Britain or America. I am thinking more about Europe. I like it more there, because in other countries I do not know the language and it would be much more difficult. But in the Netherlands there is a requirement for many people to speak English. That's the way it is. If everything comes to finding a job there. Because I just didn't want to move without work. I would like to have this affiliation to some structure, team." (MigUANF13) For her, however, it was important to be relocated to another country as part of the company rather than moving there on her own.

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(MigUANF13)

For her, however, it was important to be relocated to another country as part of the company rather than moving there on her own.

Many of our interviewees felt comfortable in Kyiv and spoke about the intentions to migrate only as a prospective life strategy rather than as a necessity. One of them was the following interviewee who said: "I would try to migrate, why not. It would be interesting for me. First, it would be interesting to see another country. And it may be some other professional growth, also it would be a different life experience. "(...) If I could choose specific countries, I would choose the Scandinavian ones, because there is a higher standard of living and social security of people at a very high level." When asked about his perception of Europe he answered:

In general, I think very positively about Europe, because European countries and the European Union, in general, are more progressive than our country. I believe that Ukraine is a third-world country. And European countries, I think, are better in all aspects: the economic situation, living standards, and respect for human rights. I would like Ukraine to grow up to European standards of living. But if I'd receive such an opportunity to try living in Europe for some time, I'd use it. (...) I think they would like to live in Europe. In one of the European countries. Probably in the one that is closer to Ukraine. Probably in Poland, Germany, because the standard of living there is quite high, and it is not very far and you can easily come to my home region, visit relatives, help them, be in touch".

(MigUASN27)

As far as the most popular destinations are concerned the aforementioned excerpt from the interview indicates some. The places with the largest concentration of Ukrainians were mentioned most frequently by our interviewees. Poland, where the number of Ukrainians is estimated to be almost 1,35 million (GUS 2020), was mentioned most commonly, however other EU countries (including Germany, Italy, Portugal, Netherlands – to mention only a few) were also frequently referred to. The countries outside of Europe that were mentioned by our interviewees included Canada, USA, Turkey and the UAE. Interestingly during the fieldwork in 2021 nobody was mentioning Russia as a prospective destination, which before the aggression on Ukraine in 2014 functioned as an important destination country for Ukrainians.

One of our interviewees who clearly was economically very comfortable in Ukraine mentioned seasonal migration out of the country to Turkey or possibly Italy for inter alia "ecological reasons". He said:

Look, we not only would like to move, but we plan to leave for permanent residence abroad. At least for some time. We are taking some action for this. Well, in particular, we bought a household in Turkey. And in general, we are there for some time, the several months that you can live in Turkey without a visa and a permanent residence permit. We spent several months with my children and wife there. And, in principle, we are considering several countries for such relaxation. Again, this depends on a variety of factors. We have worked out for ourselves such a comfortable option for us to stay without a visa. Therefore, the ideal option would probably be to live 6 warm months in Ukraine and 6 months cold ones somewhere in the south, abroad. We realised that this is the best option for us, because winter in Ukraine does not suit us. Plus the second point - this is, let's say, when you go abroad, you very clearly feel a lot of advantages in terms of living conditions. This is in terms of the quality of life, in terms of simply ecology. In Turkey, it is better. Because air pollution in Kyiv is constant, and the air in Turkey somewhere in coastal cities near the sea is of incomparable values. And it's better for kids. I think about the future of my children. Plus, of course, there is a great desire for children to receive education abroad. Also one of the driving factors for us.

(UAMigSM18)

He also very interestingly explains also how he has been tackling key issues that he and his family encountered related to financial, linguistic and educational matters. He pointed out that:

In Turkey, in principle, our budget is about the same as in Ukraine (...). The second - of course, and probably the most important - is the language problem. Well, for today it can be solved. That is, I am learning Italian and Turkish. That is, in principle, we are trying to sort of solve this language problem, despite our age. Well, for children it is generally easier because they quickly embrace the new language, new cultural contexts. The third problem is school. Since I have two children at school, there was a problem initially. Well, okay, let's move abroad, but how and where to go to school? Now we have solved this problem radically – we just transferred our children to distance schooling. So, they are not supposed to move anywhere, to any school building. That is, they just have a computer at home, and they go through all the lessons on the computer. And the efficiency of this whole process has increased significantly in comparison with school education. It is clear that there is no socialisation, communication with other children. On the other hand, there are no problems associated with this, through which we also went. Our oldest boy changed 3 schools, and in general, in each of these schools, certain nuances arose that were not related to the level of education, but related to interpersonal communication. Therefore, the Covid-19 here also became such a kind of incentive for this, and I cannot say that this is bad. So now we can leave at any time, in general, to any country for any period, and besides financially, we do not have any restrictions to do this. (UAMigSM18)

Intentional Stayers

As mentioned earlier a significant number of our interviewees argued that they do intend to migrate anywhere. Interestingly, most of the time they claimed that they are not forced to stay by different life circumstances that anchor them in this space and that do not allow them to easily live Kyiv/Ukraine, but because they feel comfortable in the city and the country or feel very strong attachment to them and hence do not want to move out.

One of our interviewees who very much saw herself in Kyiv and Ukraine argued that

"I'm not interested in other countries (maybe apart from Germany). Because I really like how I'm studying in Ukraine. I am satisfied with the education here. Everything that happens here, opportunities, I have enough of them". When asked where she see her future, she answered without hesitation "In Kyiv".
(MigUANF10)

Another interviewee who saw her future in Ukraine and stressed strong attachment to the country pointed out that "[t]he main reason is that I want to develop in Ukraine. And to do my further achievements in this country. Because now a lot of good specialists leave Ukraine and develop in other countries. And bring glory to other countries. But I want to develop here." She also said that "I am not particularly involved in migration. I was never particularly interested in this issue." (MigUANF19)

The interviewees who wanted to stay in the city and country saw their great untapped potential and their own agency. One of the was the following interviewee who argued:

Well, people just think that everything is much better there in Europe in terms of economic and in terms of some political management there, but all this can be done in Ukraine as well. We just need to put an effort, instead of thinking about any opportunities in other countries. That is, you need to look for opportunities to bring your country to a new level. Because, I believe that Ukraine has a very high potential in this regard.
(MigUANF25)

Partially her views on chances of development of Ukraine and in Ukraine were linked with the critical assessment of some of the migration narratives. She pointed out that "One may do well in this country, the other will have to go for some low-paid job and work from morning till night, and earn not much money either. There are also different attitudes towards migrants in each country. Therefore, it is also individual from the country, individually from the person himself. That is, what is his potential, how he will be able to be realised, where he will be able to find a job, housing, well, and all these moments. And how in general it will be able to adapt. That is, if a person was born in Ukraine, then he is actually tied by his family to this land, by his worldview to this country. And how he will be able to adapt to a new way of life, to a new environment. Plus there are different language elements. Well, such cultural differences. (MigUANF25) Similarly to other intentional stayers she strongly emphasised that "For now, I'm thinking about staying in Kyiv." (MigUANF25)

Yet another interviewee who stressed that he is not so much interested in further migration since he has comfortable life in Ukraine said:

"I am comfortable in Ukraine, I have a profession, I have a specialty. The only thing is that maybe my age will limit some of my migration. But I still don't feel it. (...) Higher education makes me comfortable everywhere. Because yes, because I became a specialist in business, in economics. I became a specialist, that's not what I'm bragging about. And the university gave me the trunk of these tasks. (...) If my working conditions were better abroad, I would go. And if my working conditions here are good, then why should I go somewhere, as I am comfortable working here."
(MigUANM12)

Similarly to some other stayers he also struck some patriotic note by saying "I have my homeland, which I love very much, and having worked in Europe, I always return home to my homeland." (MigUANM12)

Similarly to the aforementioned interviewee yet another one in his early 60s mentioned age as a factor that may limit his international mobility. He pointed out that "Purely theoretically – yes I can migrate. But I'm old. I'm not even interested in material things. I would just like to go to my specialty to see how they work there. I just have the wrong age. If I were young, I would go." (MigUAMLo8) He also mentioned that the only situation that would force him to migrate would be something really extreme. Like war". (MigUAMLo8)

One of our interviewees from this category who has already substantial migration experience argued that she experienced international migration and factory work (most probably not a very self-fulfilling experience) and she is not interested in it any long. She said:

"I came back (from Poland). I realised that it was not my cup of tea. I can't, I'm a different type of person. That is, I am a person when I have high peaks. That is, I can overwork, then underwork. Well, that is, in waves. And there you have to be stable. Quiet (...). I do not know how other people feel, but for me personally it was hard."
(MigUALF15)

Many of the stayers have also mentioned the chaos of the Covid-19 pandemic regulations that only enforced them in the convictions that mobility in the current age is a highly risky endeavour with which they do not want to have anything in common.

Undecided

Finally, some of our interviewees when asked about their future migration intentions stressed that they did not have a specified plan. Actually, they answered similarly to many other CEE labour migrants researched by Eade et al (2007) or Moriarty et al. (2010). In other words their answers could be classified under the categories of undecided or 'intentional unpredictability' (Eade et al. 2007) or 'deliberate indeterminacy' (Moriarty et al 2010). One of them was the following interviewee who argued that "my daughter is just still small. I didn't talk to her on this topic. I want her to grow up. Then maybe I'll plan to go to Poland for work and to take my daughter to study there. These were my thoughts. But I am still indecisive". (MigUASF29)

Other "undecided" interviewees when asked about the migration plans answered either they "have not decided yet" or "I haven't thought about it yet" (MigUASM27) or "I. It's hard to answer" (UAMigNM16). One of our interviewees who works with the IT people and is still hesitating whether it is worth moving out of the country or stay in it told us the following story that perfectly sums up elements of the hesitancy linked with the migration decision:

I had a very revealing conversation about 3 years ago, by chance in a bar. I met one guy and we got to talking with him, it turned out that he is an IT specialist. We talked for a very long time, probably about 3 hours. It turned out he had such a story that he had been living in the Netherlands for 10 years as a programmer, already providing consulting services, a rather famous dude turned out to be in narrow circles in his profile specialty, and he had already lived in the Netherlands for 10 years. It became very interesting for me, and I began to ask him, I said: how are things now? He is happy with his life. Then I told him my dreams or plans, you can say, in principle, even then I had a desire not to stay in Ukraine, but to go further to Europe. And he asks me: do you want to go to Europe because of money? Or do you want to go to Europe because you want to live there? I say: an interesting question, well, in general, both. He says it doesn't work that way. Look, he says if you need money, if your salary is interesting, then stay in Ukraine, here the salaries are the same as in Europe, but you pay much less taxes and the standard of living is not so expensive. He says: in your pocket you will have more money, I'm sure for 100%, he says. At least the first five years. But if you want to go to Europe because of the European benefits, civilizations that Europe can bestow on you, if you want to live there, because the legislation is there and there are many, many nuances for ideological reasons, then yes. Then it makes sense. I remember the conversation. And then, in principle, I only found confirmation of his words in fact around, because indeed it is. IT specialists in Europe pay a very large tax, the higher the salary, the higher the taxes. Therefore, there, with a salary of 5 thousand euros, a little more than two can remain on hand when all taxes are paid. But, housing is more expensive and everything is there. Therefore, I don't know already somehow ...
(UAMigNMo6)

Picture: Inna Kapturevska/Unsplash.com

4. Conclusion

Internal migration in Ukraine has been influenced by complex and dynamic factors. The main reasons for mobility in the time of peace are economic and they include: the lack of jobs in many regions, low salaries, little options for career choices, lower standards of life. However, there are also vital socio-cultural ones, which have become more relevant in the recent period. What's especially important in the topic of internal mobility is the uneven socio-economic development in Ukraine, which has an influence on many spheres of life: social, cultural, educational, etc. Kyiv as the capital city ranks top in terms of labour market opportunities and general standard of living. And it attracts the majority of internal migrants from various regions. Regarding internal migration flows, education comes second as the most important driver of migration after the economic ones. Rising aspiration of the youth is a relatively new factor which attracts this age group to the capital city, which offers a wide range of opportunities for self-development and personal growth. In all groups of migrants we have studied, those factors overlap and influence migration decisions.

For the current moment, environmental factors do not seem to have an impact on migration decisions. Even though there are future scenarios of negative impact of climate change (e.g. droughts) on Ukraine, and especially on the agricultural sector, these aspects are not present in migrants' narratives. This may change in the future, as negative trends would be more acute.

Political factors emerged as migration drivers regionally after 2014 in relation to Russia's occupation of Crimea and the onset of war in the eastern regions of Ukraine. Following those events, Ukraine has encountered a mass population exodus from the aforementioned regions to the state-controlled territories. Thus a significant number of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) has emerged, although not all of them are counted in the statistics. The experience of war, especially in the Donbas region, and occupation of Crimea has been a key formative factor for Ukrainian identity and an important driver of the latest wave of the Ukrainian internal (newcomers) and international migration. Russia that up to 2014 played an important role in the Ukrainian migration flows after the invasion of Crimea and Eastern parts of Ukraine has lost its previous popularity as a destination country.

In contrast to other sending countries analysed in the FUME project (Tunisia, Iraq and Senegal), there is a lack of irregular migrations from Ukraine to the European Union. The main reason is the existence of possibilities of legal migration. This is also linked with a phenomenon of asylum seekers which is an important element of migratory flows to the countries of the European Union. Although a significant number of Ukrainians who fled from the territories invaded by Russia could be eligible for some form of international protection in the European Union, very few actually use this channel of migration, preferring the economic one.

Appendix 1: Characteristics of interviewees

Symbol	Gender (M/F)	Age	Employment group*	region of origin
UAMigSF01	F	49	II	village in the Kherson region
UAMigSF02	F	32	IV	Transcarpathia, village Mizhgirya
UAMigSM03	M	29	IV	Poltava region, rural
UAMigLF04	F	38	II	Rivne region, Dubrovytsia
UAMigLF05	F	25	V	Crimea (Kerch)
UAMigNM06	M	35	III	Crimea (Bakhchisaray)
UAMigNF07	F	32	IV	Crimea
MigUAML08	M	62	III	Kherson
MigUASF09	F	32	III	Zaporozhe
MigUANF10	F	20	I	Zaporozhe
MigUALF11	F	38	IV	Crimea
MigUANM12	M	50	III	Rivne region
MigUANF13	F	33	IV	Vinnytsia
MigUANM14	M	22	I	Zhytomyr
MigUALF15	F	35	III	Titiev, Kyiv Region
UAMigNM16	M	30	II	Volynska
UAMigLF17	F	35	III	Donetsk
UAMigSM18	M	50	IV	Odessa
MigUANF19	F	23	III	Myronivka city, Kyiv region
MigUALF20	F	36	II	Donetsk
MigUALM21	M	31	III	Lugansk
MigUASM22	M	36	III	Zhytomyr region
MigUALM23	M	48	IV	Vinnytsia city
MigUANF24	F	28	III	Transcarpathia, Uzhorod
MigUANF25	F	22	I	Donetsk region

MigUALM26	M	33	III	Chernivtsi
MigUASM27	M	38	III	Zhytomyr region
MigUASF28	F	39	I	Cherkasy region
MigUASF29	F	46	II	Zhytomyr region
MigUASM30	M	31	IV	Zhytomyr city

***Employment groups:**

I – students

II - daily workers, Unskilled worker, Skilled worker or craftsman

III - Service employee or salesperson, Office worker, a technician and other middle personnel

IV - white collars - administration, high specialists, self employed, manager, supervisors, director

V – unemployed

Appendix 2: Focus group participants

Thorzhevska Tetyana Viktorivna: PhD, Anthropologist, research interests: anthropology of migration.

Polek Tina: PhD, Anthropologist, member of the Center for Applied Anthropology, research interests: migration anthropology, urban anthropology.

Khalikov Ruslan Khalikovych: PhD, Expert on Reintegration of Donbass of the Ukrainian Independent Center for Political Studies.

Oleksiy Volodymyrovych Pozniak: PhD, Head of the Migration Research Department of the M.V. Ptukha Institute of Demography and Social Studies of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine.

Malinovska Olena Anatoliivna: doctor habilitatus, Chief Research Fellow of the Department of Social Strategy of the Center for Economic and Social Research.

Adzhieva Esma: The head of the Board of Alem NGO, Deputy Chairman of the Expert Council on Intangible Cultural Heritage at the Ministry of Culture and Information Policy of Ukraine. Expert of the Ukrainian Cultural Foundation.

Appendix 3: Team of the Centre for Applied Anthropology involved in field work

Sobolieva Olena, PhD, Head of The Centre for Applied Anthropology

Ovsiuk Oksana, PhD, member of The Centre for Applied Anthropology

Mahovska Svitlana, PhD, member of The Centre for Applied Anthropology

Ktykun Julia, PhD, State Scientific Center of Cultural Heritage Protection from Technogenic Catastrophes

Anastasia Pankova, PhD, State Scientific Center of Cultural Heritage Protection from Technogenic Catastrophes

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